

Grant Agreement No.: 680708

Project acronym: HIT2GAP

Project title: Highly Innovative building control Tools Tackling the energy performance gap

Research and Innovation Action

Topic: EeB-07-2015 New tools and methodologies to reduce the gap between predicted and actual energy performances at the level of buildings and blocks of buildings

Starting date of project: 1st of September 2015

Duration: 48 months

D1.9 – Synthesis of the HIT2GAP methodology

Organisation name of lead contractor for this deliverable: EURECAT		
Version 1 – Rev.0	Due Date	M12 – 31 st of August 2016
	Submission Date	10 th of October 2016
	Primary Authors	Regina Enrich Sard (EUR)
	Contributors	NBK, EUR, FISE, BRE, BES, GIR, MOS, CYL, R2M, API, CYR, ZUT, ENE, LIU, UDG, NUIG, UOS, EGE
	Reviewers	Marcus KEANE (NUIG), Nicolas REHAULT (FISE)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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Executive Summary

The main objective of HIT2GAP is to reduce the gap between planned energy demand and real energy consumption in buildings.

The approach taken in HIT2GAP is to build an open, plug and play, application-based platform to support a new generation of Building Management Systems (BMS). This approach is seen as the effective strategy to cover user requirements in buildings that by their nature (typology, climate, usage) are widely diverse. Furthermore, it allows the platform to evolve and remain up-to-date with new emerging technologies in order to better assess energy use within a building or a block of buildings. Thus, by design the HIT2GAP platform is required to be modular and interoperable.

Although the approach proposed by HIT2GAP is generic, the project focusses on the gap reduction in commercial buildings during the commissioning and operation phases of the buildings life cycles. However, it is anticipated that the results generated by the HIT2GAP project in terms of modelling of the building behaviour may be of value to the design and construction phases of future buildings.

The HIT2GAP methodology aims to build a new generation of building monitoring and control tools based on advanced data treatment techniques allowing new approaches to assess the energy performance of buildings, getting a better understanding of the building's behaviour and hence a better performance.

HIT2GAP will enhance current BMS functionalities by:

- Using alternative sensors and meters (i.e., smart phones, mobile phones, laptops, tablets, smart watches, etc.) to capture building complexities by monitoring spaces lacking traditional sensors or to extract additional information for existing data sources (i.e. disaggregation).
- Integrating Data Mining techniques for Knowledge Discovery (DMKD) as a core module for building performance assessment and understanding, and associated predictive maintenance services.
- Adding occupants' behaviour to the equation. Taking into account that users also play a significant role in building performance, it will be possible to better understand building performance, enhance predictions and control and optimise energy consumption and occupants' comfort/health.
- Providing continuous performance evaluation and improvement based on measured, historical and simulated data coming from a new generation of simulation services.
- Integrating demand/supply management tools for building-integrated and community renewable energy sources.
- Adapting the visualization interfaces to specific user needs (technical and non-technical profiles) to deliver the information effectively.

The first version of the HIT2GAP platform will include the following application modules:

Module	Description
Load Forecasting	<p>The module is able to predict building energy consumption (for example, power consumption).</p> <p>The forecasting provides the ability to anticipate reactive behaviour.</p>
Disaggregation	<p>The module is able to separate an aggregated energy figure (for instance the total power consumption of a building as read by an electricity meter, the total hot water enthalpy flowing in a central heating network) into the various energy loads it feeds.</p> <p>Disaggregated load demand provides insight on performance and maintenance needs of energy consumer appliances.</p>
Fault Detection and Diagnosis	<p>The module provides advanced monitoring capabilities by evaluating building behaviour with respect to normal operation.</p> <p>The fault diagnosis warnings and recommendations can support the facility management to apply energy-efficient fault-free operation</p>
User Behaviour	<p>The module offers a number of services which are related to how users use the building spaces and the building energy systems.</p> <p>The user plays a key role to improve energy efficiency. The module will help to avoid energy waste by triggering alerts when misbehaviours are observed and monitor comfort parameters to adjust operation set-points to enhance health and comfort without compromising energy efficiency. Furthermore, understanding users' patterns will enhance simulation models.</p>
Multiple set-point control	<p>It provides a more affordable strategy for indoor thermal comfort of individual building spaces, taking into account occupancy patterns. It can be seen as a subset of the user behaviour module.</p>
Energy Management	<p>It provides the tool to review energy use, consumption and overall efficiency; set energy saving targets; identify energy saving opportunities; priorities and develop actions plans to meet targets for improved building energy performance, helping to develop an overall systematic approach to energy management based on ISO50001</p>

<p>Building Performance Simulator</p>	<p>The module provides the HIT2GAP platform with a model of a building and/or HVAC systems.</p> <p>The data coming from the field will help to enrich simulations and help to reduce the gap due to incorrect modelling assumptions and enabling adjustments to operation</p>
<p>Simulator-Calibration</p>	<p>This module provides with the capability to adjust the input parameters of a BPS model in order to improve the agreement between measured data and predictions.</p>
<p>Uncertainty analysis and sensitivity analysis (in simulations)</p>	<p>The uncertainty analysis provides the possibility to run simulation models with a set of uncertain input parameters (e.g. building parameters, climate conditions, occupancy). The simulation results are represented by probability distributions. Making use of uncertainty analysis methods gives the user a more reliable simulation result, as input uncertainties are taken into account.</p> <p>The module also provides methods for sensitivity analysis, which allows for determining the impact of varying input parameters on the output variation.</p>
<p>Renewable Energy Simulator</p>	<p>It is a simulation environment which serves as a design aid or decision support tool for the design or retrofit of new or existing energy infrastructures in buildings through the estimation and prediction of energy production (both thermal and electrical). It provides computations for Solar Thermal System (hot water and space heating) and Solar Photovoltaic System.</p>

1 Introduction

The HIT2GAP project aims to address the discrepancies in building energy performance between planned energy demand and real energy consumption. Although most of the newly constructed office buildings today are equipped with Building Management Systems (BMS) that integrate a more or less extended measurement layer providing large amounts of data, they do not provide any explicit functionality aimed at identifying and reducing the gap between the predicted and actual environmental and energy use profiles in buildings..

The HIT2GAP project will develop a new generation of building monitoring, performance assessment and control tools based on advanced data treatment techniques facilitating a better understanding of the building's overall environmental and energy behaviour. HIT2GAP will build on existing measurement and control tools that will be embedded into a new software platform for performance optimization.

The HIT2GAP solution will be applied as a novel intelligent layer offering new capability to the existing BMS and offering to different building's stakeholders opportunities for services with a novel added value.

This document presents a synthesis of the HIT2GAP methodology developed during the first year of the project by all project partners within *WP1 Requirements, framework and methodology to perform energy savings from data treatment*. The work carried out has led to set the technical specifications for the HIT2GAP platform in general and for all its modules.

The work has been organized in tasks tackling each of the aspects identified by HIT2GAP as crucial to reduce the gap, namely:

- Adapting the platform to user requirements (Task 1.1),
- Connecting the platform to existing BMS and to new sources of information (Task 1.2),
- Using data mining techniques for knowledge discovery (Task 1.3),
- Integrating energy modelling approaches and simulation tools with improved accuracy (Task 1.4),
- Considering user behaviour as a key element to understand energy performance and enhance energy efficiency awareness (Task 1.5),
- Improving visualization tools to deliver the information effectively to different kind of users (Task 1.6).

The results of the work conducted within the tasks have been reported in corresponding deliverables. The aim of deliverable D1.9 is to provide an overall view of the relevant aspects of the HIT2GAP solution and to provide the link to the appropriate documents for a more detailed description.

The structure of the document is as follows:

- Section 2 presents the basics of the HIT2GAP approach regarding the main features to be included in order to tackle the energy gap.
- Section 3 analyses users' requirements, including the identification of the users involved in the building energy management activities, their needs and their expectations.
- The complete picture of the HIT2GAP solution is shown in section 4, including the description of the HIT2GAP platform core, the connection layer to the modules and the visualization interface, an overview of the data model and a description of all application modules to be included in the first version of the platform.
- Section 5 presents the demonstration phase with its four pilot sites, including different buildings and different user scenarios.
- Finally, conclusions are presented in section 6.

2 HIT2GAP approach

HIT2GAP aims at designing and developing an open, plug and play, application-based platform to support a new generation of Building Management Systems (BMS) that can evolve and remain up-to-date with new emerging technologies in order to better assess the energy use within a building or a block of buildings, thus minimizing the gap between the theoretical and measured values.

The HIT2GAP framework is inspired by the smartphone Android and iOS platforms that provide a solution allowing applications to be developed separately from the platform itself and then easily integrated. Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) can develop and integrate their tools, algorithms or services within a holistic open framework and HIT2GAP uses its platform and the integrated tools to provide a new generation of BMS.

In order to address existing BMS limitations, HIT2GAP incorporates the following aspects:

- Use alternative sensors and meters (i.e., smart phones, mobile phones, laptops, tablets, smart watches, etc.) to capture and embed building complexities within the monitoring systems (e.g., try to monitor spaces lacking traditional sensors).
- Cover a wide range of energy loads, not only the so-called regulated loads (heating, cooling, hot water, lighting, ventilation) but pluggable loads as well. The involvement of occupants and the integration spread of low cost sensors allow for the monitoring and analysis of additional information to better assess the energy performance.
- Capture occupants' behaviour to provide more accurate energy performance monitoring as well as predictive control to optimise energy consumption and users' comfort/health.
- Integrate data mining techniques for knowledge discovery (DMKD) as a core module for buildings' response assessment and understanding.
- Support intelligent automated building control considering machine learning and Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques.
- Support a new generation of maintenance services where the monitored information can be used to predict maintenance requirements/scheduling.
- Integrate accuracy control using an uncertainty analysis propagation approach applied to measured data.
- Integrate demand / supply management tools for building-integrated and community renewable energy sources (with application to the pilot sites in HIT2GAP).

- Provide continuous performance evaluation and improvement based on measured, historical and simulated data (using existing tools such as ESP-r and Zutec BIM tools).
- Provide an agile integration of ISO 50001 requirements in building performance management based on the Enerit solution.
- Adapt Human Machine Interface (HMI) tools to specific user needs (e.g., experts and industrialists from different domains), developed as independent modules.
- Provide support for a new generation of simulation services that can use monitored data as an additional input to better predict energy usage.

2.1 Modularity and interoperability

HIT2GAP undertakes the challenge of defining and enabling new open solutions and products for building energy management which outperform typical “black box” proprietary solutions developed by global companies. However, HIT2GAP is not only conceived to be a platform for future BMS but also to be integrated with existing systems and tools. Thus, interoperability with existing equipment and systems is required.

In addition, buildings are built in different climates, with different resources and different BMS and will therefore always function differently under different schedules, requirements, occupants’ preferences and with different structures (open spaces, offices, residential, etc.). Due to these aspects, a single BMS cannot be adapted to all buildings and will show high and varying discrepancies between actual and predicted energy consumptions unless it can be “tuned” to building-specific qualities and characteristics. As such, HIT2GAP is designed to be modular, following a plug and play approach for integrating tools and applications, with continuous tool evaluation procedures to provide adapted solutions for each building.

The HIT2GAP modules are based on specific approaches using specific technologies for a specific target. They can be complementary or competitors, where the best performers will be retained by the facility manager.

2.2 Accuracy control

HIT2GAP is designed to follow an energy management approach, thus including accuracy and quality control mechanisms like the reference to the International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol (IPMVP) and an uncertainty assessment tool to control error propagation.

The IPMVP provides an overview of current best practice techniques available for verifying results of energy efficiency, water efficiency, and renewable energy projects. It may also be used by facility operators to assess and improve facility performance. The energy conservation measures (ECMs) covered here include fuel saving measures, water efficiency measures, load shifting and energy reductions through installation or retrofit of equipment and/or modification of operating procedures.

The IPMVP is not intended to prescribe contractual terms between consumers and providers of efficiency services, although it provides guidance on some of these issues. Once other contractual issues are decided, this document can help in the selection of the measurement & verification (M&V) approach that best matches: i) project costs and savings magnitude, ii) technology-specific requirements, and iii) risk allocation between consumer and provider, i.e., which party is responsible for installed equipment performance and which party is responsible for achieving long term energy savings.

Adjustments, mandated by IPMVP, are required to account for changes of external conditions.

Weather and occupancy information are key external parameters, suggested in the literature for use in M&V protocols. The uncertainty of such data has received significant attention. Both of them are not difficult to model and include in an IPMVP-aware analysis. Occupancy, however, shows important difficulties to measure.

Nikos Sakkas et al. [1] have analysed and published their approach with regards to IPMVP compliance in building energy efficiency. They propose three parameters whose variation may affect the performance assessment: weather, indoor conditions and building occupancy.

Calculation methods are fully defined in the reference paper [1]. In the case of weather and indoor conditions, the methods are based on variants of the “heating / cooling” hour concept. The approach has been undertaken in many practical IPMVP aware performance assessment projects by the company APINTECH which is involved in the HIT2GAP project.

With respect to the transparency of the energy savings assessment that may be conducted in the framework of Energy Performance Contracting (EPC) for instance (where IPMVP is usually used as a common guide and protocol), the energy performance gap is central as it can be considered as an important barrier for the achievement of the energy savings targeted by the contract. Therefore, the energy performance gap constitutes a strong obstacle to the deployment of EPCs. Moreover, as already stated in the DOA, an important issue associated with the rigorous implementation of IPMVP is the lack of reliable energy consumption data for the baseline period (period before the installation of the ECMs) making the evaluation of actual savings uncertain.

By removing uncertainties existing between the design data and the as-built data, HIT2GAP is able to provide a baseline more adjusted to reality and hence to reinforce the reference situation to which the actual energy consumptions will be compared (this is the case when considering new buildings in the IPMVP approach and selecting an option based on simulations of the energy performance of equipment or whole facilities to enable determination of savings when base-year or post-retrofit data are unreliable or unavailable [2]). Moreover, the uncertainty associated with the modelling of the building can be used

to strengthen the Measurement and Verification plan developed as part of each IP MVP approach, as it needs to provide uncertainty assessment corresponding to the energy savings results.

2.3 Life cycle perspective

The tools developed as part of the HIT2GAP project are aimed at acting/impacting during the commissioning and operation phases of a building. Nevertheless, the operation of the HIT2GAP tools may provide fruitful information towards the design and construction phases (virtuous loop) by establishing feedback and generic models that could be used as strengthened hypothesis for future design and construction. For instance, when conducting dynamic thermal simulations during the design phase of a building, some hypotheses are taken regarding the building occupancy and the way the building is used in terms of piloting the energy systems. A collection and a suitable analysis of the data related to these two parameters can help improving and refining the future hypotheses taken for designing a similar building.

Figure 1: Positioning of the HIT2GAP project within the building life cycle

As stated by P. de Wilde [9], the performance gap can only be bridged by a broad, coordinated approach that combines model validation and verification, improved data collection for predictions, better forecasting, and change of industry practice. That leads to recognise that the gap is not only located in the operational phase of the building life cycle as presented by MOEEBIUS¹, but it extends to other phases, such as the design phase and the commissioning phase, as depicted in Figure 1.

In this way, the HIT2GAP project can be viewed as a complementary approach to those conducted by initiatives and projects such as the BUILT2SPEC², ACCEPT³, and INSITER⁴ that are focusing on the development of tools suitable for the construction phase and aiming at reducing the gap generated during this specific phase. These projects provide specific tools dedicated to the construction actors and improve their skills through the use of tools such as a thermal imaging tool for quantitatively assessing the thermal properties of building, an airtightness test tool for quick checks, a quality check tool working as an expert tool to guarantee high quality construction work, etc.

One can imagine that outcomes from these projects can become input for the HIT2GAP project by refining the parameters used in the simulation tools and therefore improving the energy performance gap assessment.

¹ MOEEBIUS project: Modelling Optimization of Energy Efficiency in Buildings for Urban Sustainability. www.moeebius.eu

² BUILT2SPEC project: [Tools for the 21st Century Construction Worksite](https://built2spec-project.eu/), <https://built2spec-project.eu/>

³ ACCEPT project: Assistant for quality check during construction execution processes for energy-efficient buildings, www.accept-project.com

⁴ INSITER: Intuitive self-inspection techniques using augmented reality for energy-efficient buildings made of prefabricated components [\[www.insiter-project.eu\]](http://www.insiter-project.eu)

3 Users and requirements

The construction and energy management sectors are complex industries with many involved users in several stages that are also evolving to meet the changing regulations and market requests. It is crucial for projects to understand the different stakeholders' needs, desires and potential barriers to a specific implementation, development or change. By assessing the needs of each stakeholder category, proactive steps can be taken to ensure that the HIT2GAP platform is capable to fulfil these needs and to provide dedicated services. By doing this, the probabilities for success and large-scale deployments will increase. This section presents the potential relevance for different user types accordingly to their needs to the project. The results have been generated via expert knowledge, desk research and over a questionnaire which was distributed among the HIT2GAP partners. The questions had the objective to identify the needs and challenges faced by the relevant users and the features that would facilitate their activities. The content of the questionnaire can be found in appendix 9.1. Figure 2 shows the breakdown of the respondents across the 4 main stakeholder types targeted: Technology or service providers (9), Energy (3), Facility (3) and Maintenance Managers (2).

Figure 2: Breakdown of the questionnaire's respondents.

3.1 A broad view of users in building energy management

3.1.1 Potential users

Analysing the features of the HIT2GAP platform and, in general, the features of a BEMS, a list of potential users was identified, and their relevance for the HIT2GAP solutions and services was rated (see Table 1).

Table 1: List of main users with associated relevance and benefits for them with respect to the HIT2GAP platform.

User	Relevance	User	Relevance
Facility Manager	High	Technology or service providers	Medium
Energy Manager	High	Building Owner	Low
ESCO	High	Building Tenant/ Worker/ Visitor	Low
Maintenance Manager	Medium	Architect	Low
MEP Engineer	Medium		

3.1.2 Description and needs of the users

Facility Manager (FM)

The Facility Manager is a person responsible for the management of the space, services and processes that support the core business of an organisation. He ensures that an organisation has the most suitable working environment for its employees/occupants and their activities as well as an efficient space utilisation. The Facility Manager is one of the most important categories of stakeholders for the HIT2GAP platform.

Needs and Challenges

A Facility Manager is often the point of reference for the occupants in many aspects. Specifically, as indicated in the questionnaire, s/he needs to answer the occupant complaints on the basis of a thermal comfort analysis as well as an appropriate operation of the building (see Figure 29 in the appendix).

The Facility Manager is in charge of the maintenance of the building and of the building services like HVAC systems, lighting ... S/he also ensures the compliance of the building with health, security and safety policies and procedures and ensures appropriate preventive measures to limit possible health and safety risks. He can also be in charge of managing permits, authorisations and certifications rating systems (e.g., LEED, BREEAM) and he might need to collect data on waste production and recycling percentage. Finally, another need resulting from the questionnaire is to detect malfunctions and anomalies in building operation (see Figure 27).

Relevance for HIT2GAP

The Facility Manager is a key figure with respect to HIT2GAP. Several of the solutions and services being developed should facilitate the FM's job in his achievement of energy efficiency, occupant satisfaction and profit generation. Since the FM greatly interacts with occupants, tools to support the discussion with them are key factors with respect to comfort complaints and user behaviour (e.g., anomalous operation and behaviour in certain areas). Also, depending on his/her role within the organisations in terms of energy performance, modules associated with energy performance optimisation or green certification acquisition may be relevant.

Energy Manager (EM)

The Energy Manager is an individual who has to plan, regulate and monitor the energy use in an organisation or facility, with the aim of reducing the energy use while ensuring building functionalities and occupant comfort. S/he is responsible for defining the hardware and software to acquire, the equipment operation and the maintenance needs (in coordination with the Maintenance Manager, if present). The Energy Manager develops, implements and monitors environmental and energy strategies, policies and programmes that promote sustainability with the aim to improve efficiency by evaluating energy use and implementing new policies and strategies when needed. The Energy Manager should likely be the main user of the HIT2GAP platform.

Needs and Challenges

An Energy Manager (EM) needs to keep accurate records and collect energy use data and, in order to understand the typology of consumption in a building, s/he needs to generate energy use breakdown and benchmark energy consumptions against best practice guidelines (as answers from questionnaire question #2 indicate, see Figure 25 in the appendix). Decisions regarding the equipment operation (e.g., which equipment to operate, schedule, settings) are complex and important. Several factors affect the operation and the corresponding decisions have implications on finances as well as on occupant satisfaction. S/he may need to predict building energy consumption in order to develop and implement

strategies to reduce energy consumption. S/he may need to manage energy credits related to LEED, BREEAM or other rating systems and the ISO 50001 standard, carrying out site inspections and energy surveys. The replies given through the questionnaire show that the EM needs supporting information to define concrete measures to reduce energy consumptions (see Figure 23). An important challenge for the EM is to reduce the ecological footprint of the business ecosystem regarding energy consumption, but also waste, mobility, use of water and responsible consumption on site.

Relevance for HIT2GAP

The EM is extremely relevant for HIT2GAP and the tools and services being developed should facilitate the EM's complex activities with regards to forecasting loads/production, optimisation of operation based on dynamic simulation and identification of anomalous operation, just to name a few. See section 3.2 for a detailed description.

ESCo

Energy Service Companies (ESCo) provide a broad range of energy solutions including design and implementation of energy saving projects, retrofitting, energy conservation, energy infrastructure outsourcing, power generation, energy supply and risk management. They often also provide financial instruments in addition to technical services. In some cases, they deliver the financed technical solutions and are responsible for their maintenance and management.

Needs and Challenges

ESCo need to have a correct prediction of energy uses in order to structure a correct energy performance contract. They have to quantify the results of energy efficiency investments and increase certainty, reliability, and level of savings. ESCo may need to be able to predict building energy consumption based on forecasts, have access to calibrated energy simulations, and generate an energy breakdown. In cases when the contract also includes the maintenance and operation of the equipment, they are responsible for equipment operation logics and, thus, to forecast loads and identify anomalies.

Relevance for HIT2GAP

ESCo can have great benefits from the HIT2GAP platform. Since ESCo need to have a precise prediction of energy use, they can have a great support from simulation calibration and from forecasting modules. ESCo are also likely to be interested in understanding the main energy uses to concentrate the energy efficiency efforts on the main typologies.

Maintenance Manager (MM)

The Maintenance Manager is an individual responsible for the continuous running of equipment and machinery. S/he often uses computerised systems to oversee routine maintenance and schedule

repairs/regular maintenance. S/he is also involved in control and monitoring devices and occasionally in the manufacture of items that will help in maintenance. Often s/he is called when something is broken or performed incorrectly. Maintenance Managers work with other professionals in order to improve production facilities, reduce the incidence of costly breakdowns and develop strategies to improve overall reliability and safety of the plant, personnel and production processes. He/she works closely with the Facility Manager and Energy Manager to ensure correct operation and satisfaction of the occupants regarding energy across the several subsystems and facilities involved.

Needs and Challenges

The Maintenance Manager needs to have a tool that can help him/her to diagnose breakdown problems, fit new parts and make sure equipment is working correctly. For MM the main challenges which were observed from the questionnaires are: balancing of comfort needs of the building and the energy, measuring occupancy, maintaining plant hardware and equipment, need for fault alerts and maintenance management of all energy systems, understanding where overconsumptions occur and identifying causes for malfunctions. For this category emerged the importance of taking care of all malfunction fixings, adapting BMS to enable management of the energy within the building, optimisation of building controls finding a compromise between consumption and comfort, and user awareness to reduce consumptions. From the questionnaire, the need of the Maintenance Manager to detect malfunctions and anomalies in building operation (see Figure 27) and to develop an energy management system, according to the ISO 50001 standard, (see Figure 31) is evident.

Relevance for HIT2GAP

The relevance of profile is mainly represented by the need and the related tool capable of informing when the performance of a system is deteriorating, providing advanced monitoring capabilities by evaluating building behaviour with respect to normal operation. In that sense, monitoring data could help MM in adapting the maintenance actions to real conditions rather than launching them regularly. The notion of preventive maintenance instead of performing a curative maintenance is seen as a useful tool for MM.

Mechanical Electrical Plumbing (MEP) Engineer

The MEP Engineer is a qualified professional in charge of Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) and electrical and plumbing systems design. Likely, s/he is an external consultant, possibly part of the equipment contract with the manufacturer or the ESCo involved.

Needs and Challenges

The MEP Engineer needs to understand total building energy and environmental performance such as energy and fluids consumption rate and greenhouse gas emission levels, and to perform thermal building thermal simulations with detailed periodic energy consumption by use and by floor or zone. S/he also carries out an annual and monthly energy and fluids consumption survey, monitoring and

reporting. The MEP Engineer needs to support the Energy Manager and Maintenance Manager in the improvement of operation controls and identification of anomalies.

Relevance for HIT2GAP

The MEP Engineer can have some benefits from the services developed by the HIT2GAP platform, mainly related to improved knowledge about potentials for operation improvement, to enhanced energy models and fault detection and diagnosis, and forecasting elements.

Technology or service provider

Technology or service providers are developers/manufacturers that provide tools and services the different relevant figures require. They include the traditional BMS providers as well as providers of additional solutions, including: an interface showing the collected data by the BMS and that data which is not available in the current BMS functionalities; software tools providing post-processing to better manage the building in terms of energy consumptions; ISO 50001 implementation. This category includes both the developers of the solutions as well as the installers (i.e., electrician and HVAC engineers) for installations and connections.

Needs and Challenges

This group is characterised by traditional big players (BMS providers) owning a large share of the market and smaller innovative companies providing new solutions and services. Both of them need to deliver the solutions and services the clients ask for and are engaged in a competitive market. From a technical perspective, depending on the specific solutions, they need access to data for post-processing as well as building data (e.g. volume, surface, occupancy, simulations, etc.). As it turned out from the questionnaire, for Technology or service providers the main challenges are related to monitoring data acquisition and connection to existing BMS with proprietary protocols, to collection of data from the building users/occupants, to data quality, and to data analysis. Additionally, they need to develop an extensive set of interfaces to connect different kinds of sensors used to collect data that can then be used to extract knowledge.

Relevance for HIT2GAP

Technology or service providers are the developers of hardware and software components that constitute various parts of the HIT2GAP platform or must be interfaced by the HIT2GAP platform.

Building Owner

The Building Owner is an individual or entity owning the building (or set of buildings), benefitting from its revenues, responsible for paying property taxes, employees and all expenses, managing upkeep and maintenance of the building and ensuring good conditions for the building use and the increase of property value. Often, the Building Owner is an investor whose primary goal is to maximise profit.

Needs and Challenges

Building Owners need to define the costs of rent, contracts, the share of energy and fluids consumption, and the delivery of the expected value to the clients (i.e., satisfactory and functional facilities to conduct activities). Being responsible for the payment of expenses Building Owners would benefit from a reduction of energy bills as well as from a well operated building whose occupants are satisfied. Therefore, the Building Owner could be considered the final beneficiary of a successful implementation of solutions developed in HIT2GAP.

Relevance for HIT2GAP

Building Owners influence the overall goals and stimulate/hamper the utilisation. They potentially take advantage of the platform itself through an energy consumption reduction generated by the precise analysis generated from simulation calibration, the identification of faults, and the implementation of correct operation. Additionally, the tools will lead to an increased satisfaction of the occupants, which are therefore potentially willing to pay a premium price for a functional facility. The building owner may also need to have an overall visualisation of the energy information associated to the sets of buildings s/he manages in order to make some comparison between the buildings or identify the buildings which are the biggest energy consumers and then plan some refurbishment or energy conservation measures to be implemented.

Building Occupant

The Building Occupant is an individual or entity who occupies the building for residential, office or other commercial use on a regular or temporary basis. They could be tenants, workers or visitors. It is the individual who is most affected by the correct function and operation of the building (mainly via the perceived comfort conditions). Depending on the contract established the Building Occupant will or not pay for utility bills and therefore their focus may be only on comfort conditions and satisfaction. Regulator occupants have obviously bigger influence than visitors.

Needs and Challenges

Building Occupants require functional and healthy facilities with excellent comfort conditions in terms of thermal, visual, acoustic levels for a reasonable rent/cost. Their expectations must be met by the Facility Manager and Energy Manager. The cost of energy consumption can be integrated in the rent or collected as separate bills proportional to the actual consumption. The occupants and their behaviour also impact significantly the building performance and could support the achievement of an efficient building. On the contrary, inadequate behaviour leads to performance divergence and suboptimal operation. By understanding their role and the building sustainability status the Building Occupants could be more engaged.

Relevance for HIT2GAP

HIT2GAP platform provides the capability to engage the occupants by raising awareness, providing them with information they understand (not necessarily kWh) and keeping them involved and engaged in the long term management of energy. Positive engagement can reduce anomalous occupant behaviour. Building occupants can also take advantage from the platform itself by the thermal comfort improvement potentially created through the thermal comfort management modules.

Architect

The Architect is a qualified professional who outlines, plans, designs and oversees the construction of buildings. Often, the Architect is responsible mainly for the structural, functional and aesthetic features, leaving the equipment and energy aspects to the engineers working alongside.

Needs and Challenges

In relation to construction and energy management the Architect needs to estimate total building energy and environmental performance such as energy and fluids consumption rate and greenhouse gas emission levels. S/he determines energy performance labelling targets, defines procedures to get nearly zero or zero energy building levels and/or BREEAM, LEED rating systems. One of the Architect's challenges is to design a building that maximizes natural resource potential and that performs as intended. Although being responsible for the definition of the building geometry and envelope, which enhance or limit the potential for specific strategies (passive or renewable energy generation), s/he is not involved in the daily operation of the building.

Relevance for HIT2GAP

By relying on some of the solutions developed in HIT2GAP the Architect ensures that the building fulfils the expectations, minimizing issues related to operation and occupation. By understanding what did not operate correctly in one building, architects can design more robust and reliable buildings.

3.2 Scaling down to HIT2GAP users

This section presents the correlation between the needs of different stakeholders with the solutions being developed in HIT2GAP with a focus on the main actors relevant for HIT2GAP success (i.e., Energy Manager, Facility Manager and ESCo). It is a further elaboration of the previous discussion supported by the answers to the questionnaires.

3.2.1 Expectations of the users and links with HIT2GAP solutions

The main features expected from a BMS with post-processing functionalities (see answers to question #3) can be summarised as:

- Calibrated Building Energy Simulation for Maintenance Managers,
- Energy data collector and pre-processing (e.g., normalisation, codification) for Facility Managers (see Figure 33),
- Fault detection and diagnosis for both Facility and Maintenance Managers to support the identification of improvable settings (see Figure 27 in the appendix),
- Understanding occupants' behaviour supported by distributed occupancy meters, for Energy and Facility Manager (see Figure 29).

Supported by the evaluation of the questionnaires (see answers to question #4), the users expect HIT2GAP platform to:

- Provide them with a user-friendly, simple and concise interface, enabling them to go into detail of energy usage and have an intuitive and simple system allowing to easily target the causes and to identify the location generating the alerts.
- Inform users about problems or reduction in energy performance that would normally be difficult to detect at a user level by visually reviewing and comparing live, historical and expected energy usage and interacting via a 3D model.
- Strongly support the implementation of the ISO 50001 approach and to integrate the BMS with different technologies such as, e.g. FDD, model based optimization and prediction.

Based on the identified responsibilities, needs and challenges of the different users (supported by the questionnaire administration), the potential interest of each category was defined and matched with the solutions, modules and services being developed within HIT2GAP that will be further detailed later in this document. Table 2 summarises these relationships.

Table 2: Relationship between HIT2GAP Modules and Users. (LEGEND: “A” = Very Relevant, “B” = Relevant, “C” = Somewhat Relevant, and “ “ = Not Relevant)

User	Data visualization Modules	Simulation calibration	HVAC calibration	Functional Mock-up Interface (FMI)	Disaggregation	User Behaviour	Energy management	Forecasting	Building performance assessment	Fault detection & diagnosis (FDD)	Multiple set-point control	Uncertainty Analysis and Sensitivity Analysis	BIM
Facility Manager	A	C	C	C	B	A	B	B	B	A	A	C	A
Energy Manager	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
ESCo	A	A	A	A		C	A	A	A	B	C	A	C
Maintenance Manager	A	A	A	A	C	C	B	B	A	A	C	C	C
MEP Engineer	B	C	A	B	B	C	C	B	A	A	C	A	B
Building Owner	A					B							C
Building Tenant/ Worker/Visitor	A					A					A		
Architect	B	C	C	C	C				B				A

3.2.2 Focus on key HIT2GAP users

This section provides a focus on the three key users of the HIT2GAP platform: *Facility Manager*, *Energy Manager* and *ESCo*. It is an attempt to link the needs and issues they have with the proposed solutions developed in HIT2GAP.

Starting from the users' needs and issues summarised in the previous sections, we link them to the HIT2GAP modules and services that should address these major needs. Table 3 summarises the main needs and the associated modules/services of these categories.

Table 3: Connection between Facility and Energy Manager needs and HIT2GAP Modules

Users	Main Needs/Issues	HIT2GAP Modules
FACILITY MANAGER	Answer occupant complaints with quantitative data on well-being as well as appropriate operation of building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> User Behaviour Multiple set-point control
	Visualise energy and comfort related data.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data visualization modules
	Integrate with BIM database to store and visualise relevant information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BIM Visualization
	Identify anomalous operation and need for maintenance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fault Detection & Diagnosis (FDD)
ENERGY MANAGER	Run accurate simulation without detailed knowledge of dynamic simulation programs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Functional Mock-up Interface (FMI) Building performance assessment
	Equipment control optimisation. Adjust the input parameters of a BPS model in order to improve the agreement between measured data and predictions also based on sensitivity analysis.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simulation calibration Building Performance assessment Uncertainty Analysis and Sensitivity Analysis
	Characterise energy use breakdown	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disaggregation

	Predict building energy consumption (for example, power consumption)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forecasting
	<p>Manage energy credits related to e.g., LEED, rating systems, ISO 50001 standard.</p> <p>Develop, coordinate and implement strategies and policies to reduce energy consumption;</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy management
	Answer occupant complaints with quantitative data on well-being as well as appropriate operation of building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User Behaviour • Multiple set-point control • Data visualization modules
	Identify anomalous operation and need for maintenance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fault Detection & Diagnosis (FDD)
	Integrate with BIM database to store and visualise relevant information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BIM Visualization
	ESCo	Run accurate simulation without detailed knowledge of dynamic simulation programs
Correctly predict energy uses and quantify the efficacy of energy efficiency investments in order to define correct energy performance contract		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simulation calibration • Uncertainty Analysis and Sensitivity Analysis
Predict building energy consumption (for example, power consumption)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forecasting
Characterise energy use breakdown		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disaggregation
Identify anomalous operation and need for maintenance		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fault Detection & Diagnosis (FDD)

Facility Manager

As emerged from the questionnaire, this actor needs to analyse the occupants' complaints on the basis of a comfort analysis in order to answer them right, as well as appropriate operation of building by accessing data coming from different sources of information on comfort and operational conditions, and behavioural "events". The HIT2GAP Data Visualization Modules should be a significant asset for this task, given that they can provide an easy and intuitive access to real-time and historical energy consumption data through visualization techniques. Other related tools are 'User Behaviour' and 'Multiple set-point control': the first one allows to monitor user behaviour and influence behavioural changes through the use of background information on how users perceive comfort; the second one allows to maintain different indoor comfort levels depending on the occupancy profiles through the adjustment of a 3-way valve or a thermostatic valve. Another aspect detected in the questionnaire is to have an easy-to-use visualisation of a building's current and historical performance in the same platform with BIM and Operation & Maintenance (O&M) data. The BIM module can fulfil this need since it is capable not only to visualize the space temperature/humidity/energy usage (current and historical) but also the variation from design along with the manufacturers details, as built drawings, planned and reactive maintenance details, spare parts and maintenance procedures among others. Finally, Facility Managers can perform continuous monitoring of building services to conduct anomaly detection or routinely assess the correct state of systems and components; the use of the fault detection and diagnosis (FDD) module can provide advanced data mining capabilities by evaluating building behaviour with respect to normal operation.

Energy Manager

The EM is a key figure and potentially the main user of the HIT2GAP platform. For this reason, all the HIT2GAP modules are important and necessary to satisfy EM needs, beginning from the HIT2GAP Building Performance Assessment tool and its related modules calibration, Building Performance Simulation (BPS), and uncertainty Analysis and Sensitivity Analysis: these modules allow to optimize the performance of the systems and to evaluate energy efficiency options that might be cost-effectively deployed or to deploy a Building Performance Assessment tool in model predictive control mode. The HIT2GAP Disaggregation module can provide an EM with the ability to separate an aggregated energy figure into the various energy loads with much greater knowledge extrapolated to understand the main causes of consumption, without the need for sub-metering. The Energy Management module provides support for the requirements of ISO 50001 standard, namely access to energy use data with focus on deviations in order to take corrective actions, allowing data acquisition and remote monitoring, etc. Finally, the BIM integration can give a visual and easy-to-use view of a buildings current and historical performance on the same platform that BIM and O&M data is available.

ESCo

Since ESCOs have the need to have a correct prediction of energy uses and to quantify the results of energy efficiency investments in order to design a correct energy performance contract, it can have a great support from simulation calibration and from the forecasting module. These innovative tools will provide ESCo with confidence regarding their equipment operation predictions as well as detailed time resolution to reduce investment risks.

Ideally, the ESCo would be supported by the FDD module, informing promptly about anomalies, maintenance needs or incorrect operation/behaviour. The ESCos are also surely interested in understanding how the energy consumptions are distributed in order to concentrate the energy efficiency efforts on the main typologies. This makes the disaggregation module relevant, which allows to create an energy data analysis split to categories without the need of sub-metering devices.

4 HIT2GAP Platform and Modules

4.1 Platform requirements

Nowadays, Building Management Systems (BMS) in smart buildings face several challenges, such as interoperability with other systems, being closed proprietary solutions or lack of data analysis. As a matter of fact, interoperability issues arise on different levels:

- **On the field level**, due to the existence of various devices/sensors that are developed by different manufacturers and that communicate over different protocols.
- **On the management level**, due to the existence of different third-party applications developed on different environments/platforms and written in different languages.
- **Between the field level and the management level**, since on the one hand, any modification applied on the field level (i.e., additional types of devices) requires an adaptation of the applications and services on the management level. On the other hand, any changes embedded in the applications of the management level, affect the configurations of the physical equipment on the field level.

Moreover, existing BMS solutions act as black boxes that cannot be modified to extend their functionalities and thus be adapted to new environments or to meet other business requirements.

In addition, current BMS tools lack data analysis and advanced data processing functionalities that can support Facility and Energy management tasks. The current development in the fields of artificial intelligence, data mining techniques, and machine learning offer an interesting potential for BMS solutions where large amount of data is being collected from multiple devices and equipment.

In order to cope with these challenges, the HIT2GAP architecture should cover the following requirements schematically displayed on Figure 3:

- **Modularity:** allows different modules to be added or replaced on the upper level without affecting the rest of the system.
- **Scalability:** can be easily extended to meet other business requirements.
- **Field Interoperability:** ensures the integration among diverse systems/devices that are developed by different manufacturers and communicate via different communication protocols.
- **Middleware Interoperability:** ensures seamless communication between the field and the management levels.
- **Management Interoperability:** integrates different management applications/modules

developed by different parties and facilitates the information exchange between them.

- **Advanced processing and analysis:** embeds artificial intelligence techniques (i.e. ontologies, data mining, machine learning, etc.) to obtain valuable information.
- **Genericity:** applicable and adaptable to different environments and types of buildings.

Figure 3: Requirements identified for the HIT2GAP solution

The main idea of HIT2GAP is to design and develop a generic open platform where third parties provide analytic software and services including simulation services to optimize building energy performance and reduce the gap between the conceptual intent and actual performance. In order to achieve the scope of the HIT2GAP project, the platform architecture is to be formed in two distinct parts: 1) the platform core, consisting of a set of core functionalities that enable connectivity to BMS and alternative devices/sources, data collection, pre-processing and normalization, and Open access to Third-Party applications, 2) the application platform, which includes the modules developed by third parties (in this case, consortium members). The concept for connecting the platform core with the application modules can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4: HIT2GAP concept description

4.2 The HIT2GAP Platform Core

The HIT2GAP platform core is a middleware between the field level (pilot sites) and the management level (application level). It consists of 3 main layers (i) Data Collection, (ii) Information, and (iii) API Layers as can be seen in Figure 5 .

Figure 5: HIT2GAP architecture

4.2.1 Data Collection Layer

The Data Collection Layer is responsible for the data collection, normalization and preparation, and includes 2 sub-layers, a Drivers/Data Connectors' layer and a Data Model layer.

- The **Drivers/Data Connectors' layer** contains different drivers and connectors that connect to the data sources existing in the Field level (e.g., PLAT.ONE is used as a connector to the pilot sites). These connectors include all specific information related to the technologies used in the Field level (i.e., communications protocols, type of devices, configurations, etc.). This covers the horizontal approach paradigm, allowing devices to be added and removed (horizontally) as required without affecting other levels.
- The **HIT2GAP Model layer** plays an essential role in effectively separating the lower Field level from the upper Management level. This layer includes a data model, a storage space, a Data Preparation module and a Model Builder module.
 - The HIT2GAP Data Model is based on a semantic representation (in our case Ontologies). It contains, on the one hand, technical and functional information on all types of equipment and devices available in the Field level (i.e., what each device does, what type of data these devices capture, how these devices and equipment are connected, etc.) which is used to store the collected data, and on

the other hand, information regarding the I/O of energy management modules that will be used to retrieve and store data to/from the upper level applications and services (e.g., the predicted data from the prediction module can be stored and then retrieved by a visualization module afterwards). The data model will be as generic and complete as possible to cover the field and management levels requirements.

- The Storage Space is used to store all the data collected from the field level and the management level based on the HIT2GAP Data Model. The storage space can be on the cloud or on a dedicated server based on the specifications and requirements of the HIT2GAP approach.
- The Data Preparation module is used to clean and prepare the data. In other words, this module handles outliers and missing data. Missing data can be corrected using extrapolation, interpolation or aggregation functions.
- The Model Extender module is used to allow third-parties to extend the HIT2GAP Data Model with new concepts to accommodate the specifications of their management or field module (this module will not be developed in the first version of the HIT2GAP prototype due to time limitations).

4.2.2 Information Layer

The Information Layer is mainly responsible for reasoning on the Ontology (the data model) using building indicators to elaborate meaningful information related to building energy management. At this stage of the project, this layer remains undefined as the priority falls on the main data model that is required before the definition of the reasoning process.

4.2.3 API Layer (Open Access Layer)

The API Layer is responsible for defining an interface that will be used by the Consortium and other third-parties to adapt their tools. It contains APIs accessible by the Management level applications and services. The functionalities offered by those common APIs ensure the interoperability of different applications and services on the upper level since any additional or required application can use the APIs to connect the HIT2GAP data storage to send and retrieve any required information without affecting other applications or services. The HIT2GAP API will be used mainly to integrate any module defined by third-parties. It is conceived as a web service independent from any platform and development language. This will allow third-parties to integrate their modules using their specific development expertise. To simplify the integration of modules, a specification document will be provided detailing the different queries and functionalities of the API. The output data will be formatted in JSON, XML or CSV based on the specifications of the API and the data collected within the platform. When a visualization or a treatment module is being developed for HIT2GAP, it will use the HIT2GAP API to send a request to retrieve or store data collected by the core platform from the

pilot sites. The API will send a response with the corresponding data. It is critical to note that the modules will communicate vertically with each other through the platform core. They will not communicate directly with each other, unless they are considered a single module.

4.3 The HIT2GAP Data specification: an introduction

This section introduces the data specification of HIT2GAP. However, it is meant to be a summary, since the complete HIT2GAP data specification can be found in the deliverable D1.2 [8]. In the above mentioned document the following aspects are covered:

- Identification of key elements involved in measuring building performance,
- Demonstration of the absence of existing referential data models for building performance by exploring existing data models and standards,
- Specification of HIT2GAP integrated and referential data model.

As a summary, it is worth to note that the HIT2GAP platform needs to integrate different data sources into one referential model: building information, traditional sensors (e.g., humidity, surveillance camera, etc.), smart sensors (e.g., smartphones, smartwatches, etc.), solutions/modules (analysis, diagnosis, prediction, etc.) from different providers on several levels, and occupant activities and behaviour, in order to optimize the building energy consumption.

In order to improve the building energy efficiency, the solution to be developed must consider the complexity of a building, which includes:

- Multiple subsystems designed for heating, ventilation, air-conditioning, lighting, electricity, communication, etc.,
- Multiple actors and occupants having different behaviours and needs,
- Various interactions with its outdoor environment.

The data model must include the following aspects:

- **Data about buildings:** the Building Information Model (BIM) needs to be used (when such information is available) as a shared knowledge. Several data need to be taken into account:
 - Layout and spaces,
 - Location and orientation,
 - Thermal properties of all elements such as walls, floors/roofs/ceilings, doors, windows, etc.,
 - Functional usage and purpose,

- Space conditioning requirements.
- **Data about building equipment:** a building is often equipped with a number of devices (sensors, actuators, and meters) used to operate its automation such as:
 - Energy and water meters,
 - Temperature and humidity sensors,
 - Pressure and flow meters,
 - Internal loads, power energy and storage capacity,
 - Heating, Ventilating, and Air Conditioning (HVAC).

The data size collected from the equipment depends on the complexity of the building services, the level of sensorization and the sampling rates.

- **Data about activities and occupancy:** the sensing technologies and measurements are important to consider since they are attracting more and more attention as a means of monitoring indoor building activities and space occupancy. They could be connected to the building (e.g. occupant and light sensors, noise sensors, movement, etc.) or to the occupants (e.g. smart phones and watches). Also, other data could be of capital importance such as schedules for lighting, future scheduled events, etc.
- **Data about occupants:** It is important to adapt the energy consumption not only according to the occupant activities but also according to their preferences and profiles in order to reduce energy costs and provide personalized comfort. This allows also recognizing problems and identifying priorities in maintenance tasks. To do so, data about occupants needs to be collected from different sources: building and user sensors, questionnaires, social networks, etc.
- **Data about/from applications:** data driven solutions have been implemented for various energy efficiency efforts varying from energy performance evaluation (using energy models or statistical data), cooling and heating load prediction (using historic load data and/or data-driven regression models), energy model auto-tuning (to provide efficient retrofit measures), to optimal building controls (using data-driven regression models).
- **External Data:** Data can also come from outside the building. Meteorological data are always needed in predicting energy needs in a building. They could come from BMS, dedicated sensors and equipment, but also from the web. Also, social networks can allow for detecting some important events related to the location of the building (earthquake, flooding, etc.).

The collection of these different kinds of data is fundamental for the HIT2GAP solution to meet its objectives and to provide appropriate tools for building operators to identify energy-related problems, to monitor and to adapt energy operation of their facilities.

Furthermore, the HIT2GAP data model must be aligned with the features of the HIT2GAP architecture design principles presented in section 4.2 in the sense to meet the following requirements:

- **Global Integration and Interoperability:** The data model must ensure integration and interoperability of the different data sources previously mentioned related to Buildings, Occupants, Sensors, BMS, and Energy equipment/systems. This is a big challenge since they are heterogeneous and created in different formats on different platforms.
- **Knowledge-based:** The data model must provide a wrapping between data, information and knowledge to allow better understanding, analysis and decision-making.
- **Evolutionary:** The data model must provide a means to enrich existing data/concepts. The data model must also allow new modules to be added or replaced without affecting the rest of the system.
- **Genericity:** The data model must be applicable and adaptable to different environments (BMS, sensors, etc.) and types of buildings (residential, commercial, administration, etc.). Systems/devices can be developed by different manufacturers and parties.

4.4 The Application Modules

This section presents the main application modules to be included in the HIT2GAP platform which are developed and tested within the HIT2GAP project. The modules will be developed by partners of the consortium. As mentioned above, the set of application modules could be extended in the future by third party developments. The modules have been selected according to the requirements captured from the users (see section 3) and their impact in the gap reduction. For each module a summary table is presented expressing its main features, targeted users, input and output data and interfacing requirements.

4.4.1 Forecasting

Short-term load forecasting models are of special interest for energy management because they give the possibility to anticipate reactive behaviours. The extraction of information and knowledge (patterns recognition and tracking in data) from the monitored data (energy consumption, ambient weather conditions, and occupancy) can support maintenance scheduling as well as the understanding and optimising of the energy operation of buildings.

Short term energy consumption forecasting consists in building a model where the influence of other variables allows estimating the consumption. Although usually occupancy and temperature are the variables that best explain consumption in buildings, the relation among them is not always direct or other variables can contribute to refine such models. The selection of variables and the development

of a model structure are crucial tasks and have implications on the performance of the forecasting model.

However, the existence of blank, corrupted or wrong data and outliers has a great influence on the model outputs and has to be overcome by filtering methods. That is the reason why the HIT2GAP core platform will include in the data collection layer the Data Preparation module with pre-processing functionalities. Finally, it is also common to normalize data in order to avoid dominance effects due to large magnitudes of some variables. After this pre-processing, the available data is organized in matrices where columns correspond to variables and rows to observations at the same timestamp. Resampling of data can be required in some cases. It is also necessary to include some service in charge of subsampling data from the data base with two purposes, validation and model refinement.

As presented in D1.3 [4] in the technical specification of the dynamic, data based and short term forecasting functionality of HIT2GAP, forecasting models are usually parametric models that require adjusting some parameters by applying a supervised learning algorithm. According to literature [10], [11], the multiple linear regression (MLR), multilayer perceptron (MLP) and support vector regression (SVR) usually perform very well. Nevertheless, there is not a single method which outperforms others, and the quality of the results depends on the variables involved (load, weather, etc.), building type (malls, offices, university campus, simulated buildings, etc.) and climate type (Mediterranean, Oceanic, Continental, etc.). Since often the results are ambiguous, comparing different methods is helpful. At the same time it is necessary to provide performance indicators (e.g, correlation coefficient –CC- or the mean absolute percentage error –MAPE-) in order to facilitate the election of the best method. In HIT2GAP, the three methods mentioned above will be included.

Table 4: HIT2GAP Forecasting module specification

HIT2GAP Forecasting module	
Purpose and rationale	<p>The module is able to predict building energy consumption (for example, power consumption). Data-based predictive models will be integrated in the module for load forecasting.</p> <p>The rationale behind forecasting is the ability to anticipate reactive behaviour.</p>
Users	Energy/facility manager with data mining skills.
Conditions required for the implementation	<p>The availability of historical data spanning a sufficient period of time will be needed in order to include sufficient variability in building behaviour. These data are power consumption and weather information, such as temperature, irradiance, humidity, etc., outdoors and/or indoors, gathered at the same time.</p> <p>Pre-processing and cleansing techniques are needed to ensure good data quality.</p>

	In order to exploit the forecasting models, it is needed to have on-line data corresponding to the same variables that were selected for building the models.
Data required	<p><u>Data nature:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Historical data from sensors equally sampled (typically hourly) depending on detail of the analysis requirements and with a common time reference. Examples include: energy measurements, temperature (indoor/outdoor), humidity, occupancy, etc... - Calendar data. - New data (same variables as used as inputs during the model creation). <p><u>Dependence on data format:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tables (variables in columns and observations in rows). Each row has to refer to the same timestamp (typically 1 hour). - Current formats accepted: DB tables, csv, arff, xls.
Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Output is a model (MLR, MLP or SVR), performance indicators (RRSE, r, etc.) and predictions (charts). - The model is an object containing the relationships among variables or a list of vectors or weights. - The predictions are numeric values (forecasting data vector). - The performance indicators are numeric values. - Some outputs are exportable to xls or csv.

4.4.2 Disaggregation

Disaggregation techniques enable the assessment of the energy consumed at various loads without the need for their separate metering (sub metering); thus, it is a non-intrusive and cost- efficient approach to track load performance and, therefore, identify maintenance needs or even inappropriate and energy-unconscious user behaviour.

In the typical disaggregation scenario, it is not necessary to consider all loads; but only to focus on loads which have some particular interest.

Disaggregation dates back to the early 1980s with the work of George W. Hart at MIT. Since then multiple approaches have been developed. Most of the load disaggregation techniques rely on high frequency measurements (~10 kHz) which exploit the harmonic signatures left by each appliance. However, sampling at this rate presents a great number of practical problems, among them the huge amount of data generated, and is far from the current state of the art. Research and commercial implementations are now favouring a low frequency approach, e.g. CSEM (CH) developed a technology that relies on low frequency and in particular 1Hz measurements. This approach is technically easy to implement, and has the advantage of being compatible with the current smart energy meters. Sampling at such low frequencies, however, compromises the accuracy, with the accuracy further reduced as the number of devices increases. Supplementary monitoring is

sometimes used with low frequency sampling to enhance accuracy, e.g. a device start signal coincides with water flow detected by a flow switch thus indicating a heating burner. The problem with this approach is obviously additional instrumentation.

A more extended analysis of the disaggregation module including a review of the methods for energy disaggregation, scenarios where energy disaggregation may be applied and technical requirements of the disaggregation can be found in D1.4 [5].

The disaggregation module to be developed within HIT2GAP will follow a three tier approach, matching the following sequence:

- **Tier One:** The first tier addresses easy to map cases, and aims at identifying obvious patterns via the start signatures of specific devices. In the usual case the approach of Tier 1 will filter out the easy loads but will be unable to completely disaggregate the consumption.
- **Tier Two:** The second tier is called upon to look at the remaining, usually the majority of the electric devices. The technology here is pure signal disaggregation, whereby the aggregated consumption is broken down to the device level and device level information is extracted. While the Tier-One approach caters for easily identifiable cases, Tier-Two will analyse the rest through in-depth disaggregation analysis. The HIT2GAP approach uses an in-between sampling frequency of the aggregated signal between 20-30Hz. In addition, this sampling frequency allows for identifying the rush in current of electric devices upon their start up. This rush in the signature allows for fully and accurately modelling each device. Depending on the device the rush in current typically lasts between 50ms up to 1-2 sec. With a sampling at ~20Hz, in the great majority of cases it will be possible to trace the rush in current and accurately identify the device.
- **Tier-Three:** This tier is based on the use of modelling; it is called in for assistance when the two above tiers are not certain about how to disaggregate some pattern, possibly because of signatures being very similar. By having programmed usage models of all devices this information can assist the disaggregation process.

Table 5: HIT2GAP disaggregation module specification

HIT2GAP Disaggregation module	
Purpose and rationale	The disaggregation module is able to separate an aggregated energy figure (for instance the total power consumption of a building as read by an electricity meter, the total hot water enthalpy flowing in a central heating network) into the various energy loads it feeds.
Users	Facility managers, maintenance technicians are the primary users of disaggregation services; end users are involved, although rather indirectly as potential recipients of recommendations.

<p>Conditions required for the implementation</p>	<p><u>Obligatory</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The total consumption in time, collected via an energy meter of the aggregated energy information, i.e., Depending on the type of the disaggregation carried out this may be electric, hot water, oil, gas, etc. This metering provides the basic data that needs to be disaggregated to a number of [n] loads. • The signatures of these loads; a signature is the typical start curve of the load. For example if a load is an AC motor its signature will be its start-up transient response, i.e., the current curve when the motor starts up. This is quite distinctive of the load and is the key information for “hunting” and discovering the load in the collective curve. Depending on the type of the load the signatures: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - may be modelled via direct metering, - may be approximated via their technical information; in principle resistive loads (lighting, etc.) are easy to model and incorporate in the signature database. <p><u>Helpful but non obligatory</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usage models, i.e., knowledge of the use patterns of the loads can be helpful in tracing them, especially in cases where signatures may be very similar. For example if two loads present the same signature but one is used in the morning only and the other in the afternoon, then this information is highly important for the tracking of the particular load.
<p>Data required</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • device signatures (tier 1), via direct entering in the device model . This may be a small number between 1-10 data items that model the device. • device start-up signatures (tier 2), via scanning at 20-30 Hz for 3 sec. A table of ~100 data items, per device will result. • the usage model (tier 3), if available, of all devices. This is a structure like the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - use time start [], accuracy % [], - use time duration [], accuracy % [], - max values[], accuracy % [], - min values [], accuracy % [], - repetitive []. <p>The aggregated energy needs to be ideally continuously scanned at 10-30Hz. This is necessary in order to trace the device transient response during start-up. This will result in $10-30 \times 60 \times 60 \times 24 = 0.8 - 2.5$ million measurements per day, a figure that can be significantly reduced if it is known that the target devices are not operational within certain periods of the day.</p>

	In any case this figure is within the capacity of energy meters both for scanning as well as for storage.
Output	<p>For all modelled devices :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • their timing and consumption data are reported, • possible malfunctioning or improper operation incidents are identified. <p>Results are communicated to the users, facility managers or end users</p>
User interface requirements	To be developed

4.4.3 Fault detection & diagnosis (FDD)

The research community has developed a number of methods for detecting faults in buildings and heating, ventilating, and air-conditioning systems (HVAC), as widely presented in D1.3 [4] covering the technical specification of the dynamic, data based and short term forecasting functionality of HIT2GAP. The monitoring process performed in a building takes advantage of a model created by means of a selection of methods with data during normal operating conditions. This model serves as a reference model to detect deviations (residuals or discrepancies) that can be considered abnormal (faults, anomalous behaviour, disturbances, over-consumption, efficiency losses, etc.). Typical tasks include alarm generation, fault detection, fault isolation, fault diagnosis and fault response according to some modelling strategy. The understanding of energy consumption patterns can help to define and evaluate the new design requirement of buildings and to evaluate the effectiveness of energy conservation measures as well.

The following figure (Figure 6) represents the general procedure, which can be subdivided into two parts: The training procedure (on the left) is required to obtain the model and is usually performed off-line (with historical data). The application procedure (on the right) involves monitoring, fault detection and diagnosis and is performed on-line every time new data is available.

Figure 6: FDD general procedure

Some definitions are needed to better understand the description of the module to be implemented in HIT2GAP.

Definition 1: FDD Model

The FDD model is a classification model trained on historical (classified) data which allows for the classification (i.e. fault detection) of previously unknown data. The training procedure is typically based on machine learning methods and data mining approach principles.

For example, the FDD Model can include a representation of the building energy consumption given by relationships between the observed variables. If the monitored building energy consumption does not match (within a certain range) the predicted energy consumption by the FDD model, the FDD model classifies the corresponding observation period as abnormal or faulty. Remarks:

- A Normal Operation Conditions (NOC) FDD Model is obtained with data that is collected during normal operating conditions of the building. Depending on the employed method, FDD models can also use data corresponding to faulty operation for training and validation.
- Data used for training and validations requires some quality conditions achieved by a pre-treatment procedure.
- Usually an energy model relates a set of independent variables (e.g., occupancy, weather conditions, temperature, etc.) with the building consumption vectors.

Definition 2: Fault signature

A fault signature is a vector that gives information related to the measured variables that can be interpreted once a fault is detected in order to infer information about location and/or magnitude of the fault. The fault signature describes the responsibilities of individual variables/sensors for a detected fault and serves as input for fault diagnosis.

Some FDD methods use a measure of the deviation of the observation from the normal operation model (residual). Residuals are indicators that measure the distance or degree of discrepancy between new data and the prediction of a reference model. Thus, the better the match between new data and the model predictions, the lower the magnitude of residuals (close to zero). In such methods a threshold is used to decide about the normal or fault situation.

Definition 3: Diagnosed fault

A diagnosed fault is a vector with as many components as diagnosable elements, that contains ones for the component or components responsible for the fault and zeros for any component operating normally.

A diagnosed fault (e.g. “stuck heating coil valve”) can directly be passed in form as a fault report to the management / visualization level.

The rationale behind FDD is to supervise the building behaviour, in terms of energy consumption, comfort requirements and proper controls by continuously analysing the monitored data with respect to the reference model (FDD model). In case of discrepancies, the generation of alerts to energy managers and an accurate location of possible causes can reduce energy waste considerably. At the same time, the reference model provided by the FDD methodology can also be exploited for energy forecasting giving a prediction for the independent variable.

The module to be developed within HIT2GAP has two functionalities: energy building modelling (setup FDD model) and monitoring/exploitation (application of FDD model), including Fault Detection and Diagnosis.

- **FDD modelling (setup):** The module allows the user to create data driven models based on historical information provided by sensors, including energy consumptions, occupancy, weather information, and similar sampled variables. These models will serve as a reference to distinguish between normal operation and faulty operation.

The basic steps to create a model are the following:

1. Select variables of interest.
2. Select periodicity/seasonality in the data.
3. Selection of training and testing data sets.
4. Model training.
5. Model validation.

- **FDD monitoring (exploitation)**: The module allows the user to monitor a building or neighbourhood (all the associated variables being acquired) using a selected model. New observations are evaluated using the FDD model and classified accordingly.

The basic steps to exploit a model with a set of new observations are the following:

1. Select a model.
2. Configuration: Select parameters (thresholds, confidence level, etc.) if any.
3. Classification of input data (based on computation of residuals or other approaches).
4. According to classification: fault alarm generation.
5. Fault identification: Determination of fault signature (in case of abnormal operating conditions).
6. Fault diagnosis: evaluation of fault signature, generation of diagnosis and impact estimate.

Table 6: HIT2GAP Fault Detection and Diagnosis module specification

HIT2GAP Fault detection and diagnosis	
Purpose and rationale	The fault detection and diagnosis (FDD) module provides advanced monitoring capabilities by evaluating building behaviour with respect to normal operation. The analysis is based on a model (FDD model) which is trained beforehand with historical data corresponding to normal operation condition (NOC) and / or faulty operation. The training and validation procedure typically involves machine learning methods, but might also comprise expert knowledge to some extent. Application of the FDD model to new data allows for the detection of abnormal operating conditions (AOC) as faults and failures in sensors or technical equipment or user misbehaviour, for example. Once a fault or an abnormal condition is detected, the module analyses in a further step possible reasons for the observed misbehaviour. Thus, the AOC can be associated with a certain subsystem or an individual sensor and it even might be related to a specific fault type. The identification of the reason for a detected fault (diagnosis) can directly be used for evaluating the (energetic or financial) impact of the fault.
Users	Energy manager, Facility manager
Conditions required for the implementation	For modelling, the availability of historical data during sufficient period of time to gather variability on building behaviour is mandatory. This historical data has to be classified in the sense that it is known whether the data corresponds to normal operation or faulty operation. A database with training and validation data for this

	<p>purpose would yield a great benefit for the HIT2GAP platform, as developers of FDD methods can compare their methods against existing ones in the platform. In addition, data is needed to be pre-processed and cleansed to guarantee its quality.</p> <p>For model exploitation (monitoring, fault detection and fault diagnosis), it is necessary to have on-line measurements of the same variables that were used in the model creation. Also, on-line data has to be cleansed.</p>
<p>Data required</p>	<p><u>FDD modelling (setup):</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classified historical data from sensors equally sampled (15 min, hourly, daily...) depending on detail of the analysis requirements and with a common time reference. For example, energy measurements, temperature (indoor/outdoor), humidity, occupancy, etc. The majority of learning/modelling algorithms require as input a matrix where columns represent variables and rows observations. • Building parameters. <p><u>FDD monitoring (exploitation)</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On-line data (same variables as used in the model creation), usually a single dated vector is used (a sample every hour for example), but multiple samples in the period can be considered (daily profile sampled hourly – 24 samples–).
<p>Output</p>	<p><u>FDD modelling (setup):</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Output is a FDD model ready for monitoring tasks and its associated performance indicators and parameters (decision thresholds, confidence factor, etc.). • Optionally, the model can be visualised using scatter plots and charts to assist the model creation procedure. <p><u>FDD monitoring (exploitation):</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Residuals (if the method provides this information), • Fault signature, • Fault diagnosis.
<p>User interface requirements</p>	<p>-</p>

4.4.4 User Behaviour

Behavioural change is admitted to be the next big frontier towards building energy efficiency. Even though energy systems are more and more optimized and contribute to energy saving, it is only behavioural change that carries the promise of major savings in practically all types of the building stock, regardless of building type and use, or age. Studies show that behavioural and social insights going beyond simple assumptions of rational economic decision-making make possible significant reductions in energy consumption by households and organizations at short to intermediate temporal scales [12]. It is in this strategic perspective that the behaviour module, (called hereafter 'the BM') has been designed.

With the exception of the “mood component”, the module functionalities are technically based on behavioural “events” that the module processes and uses to trigger some “reaction”. This reaction may include one or more of the following.

- a notification to the space users; notification is a key mechanism towards behavioural change. Notifications will be carried out typically via the following three channels;
 - dashboards
 - e-mails
 - SMS

Other additional options may be considered but are not supported by the first version of the BM.

- a suggestion / implementation of a change of practice; this can be
 - behavioural change
 - technology implementation aiming at greater energy efficiency and/ or indoor quality
- a validation of the change of practice
 - objectively; via measurements and impact calculation
 - subjectively; via questionnaires and satisfaction surveys

In order for the 'event – reaction' pair to work it is often necessary to use “background information” on how users perceive comfort, etc. This information may be collected via questionnaires and other non-real time means. In a way, this information parameterizes the target space and its users.

The approach is modular; the functionalities below represent a first version (BM, version 1.0) to be implemented and demonstrated within HIT2GAP; the vision and the long term perspective on the BM is presented in D1.6 [6] where the technical specification for user behaviour is described.

The mood component is not event-driven; the mood component registers and reports on the mood of a number of users; this can be then used for any sort of relevant analyses.

The following diagram in Figure 7 illustrates the generic module architecture.

BEHAVIOR MODULE- Functionalities

Figure 7: Functionalities of the Behaviour module

Table 7: Summary of events defined in Behaviour module ver 1.0

Event	Trigger	Reaction	Validation
Lighting on under no occupancy/presence	A digital on/off occupancy detector or headcount sensor senses a no presence condition ⁵ , and the Lighting status is ON.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - via simple notification: The BM module issues a reminder and a recommendation to space users that have this type of notification ON; the notification can be received by all three standard channels; dashboard, e-mail, SMS. - via technology change: Presence sensors are now interlocked with the light switching and turn the lights off immediately or with some programmable delay. Notification may or may not be sent out to users. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If the technology change has been adopted, the achieved savings via the switching can be assessed by calculating the time between switching the lights off and on (or rather next time presence was detected in the space) and multiplying it by the wattage of the lighting system. - If the technology change has not been adopted one can only rely on the users and their subjective perception of the achieved savings; short questionnaires collect and process this info.
'high' (in winter) and 'low' (in summer) indoor temperature settings under no occupancy/ presence	A digital on/off occupancy detector or headcount sensor senses a no presence condition. The heating/ cooling set-point remains in HIGH position even after a configure time goes by.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - via simple notification: The BM module issues a reminder and a recommendation to space users that have this type of notification ON; the notification can be received by all three standard channels; dashboard, e-mail, SMS. - via technology change: Presence sensors are now interlocked with the thermostat and change its value. The module does not produce an output, as the HVAC can have 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If the technology change has been adopted, the achieved savings can be calculated in terms of heating/cooling. If one is to translate these hours into energy (kWh) some simulation of the space will be required. It would be complex and expensive to measure energy savings directly and thus, this is to be avoided. - If the technology change has not been adopted one can only rely on the users and their subjective perception of the achieved savings;

⁵ The presence detector is considered a more safe and cost efficient way for this event.

Event	Trigger	Reaction	Validation
		<p>many configurations making this difficult to standardize. It seems more reasonable to just change the thermostat setting down to MEDIUM or LOW. Notification may or may not be sent out to users.</p>	<p>short questionnaires collect and process this info.</p>
<p>'Low indoor comfort under presence conditions'</p>	<p>The event traces low comfort conditions of an operational space (presence ON); defined as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ambient temperature outside a specific range - ambient temperature variation exceeding a specific percentage - ambient humidity outside a specific range - surface temperature outside a specific range <p>Not all four options need to be simultaneously set and traced in the BM</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - via simple notification: The BM module issues a reminder and a recommendation to space users that have this type of notification ON; the notification can be received by all three standard channels; dashboard, e-mail, SMS. - via technology change: It does not appear possible to hardwire any predefined technology solution. If there are comfort issues one needs to understand their origin and then take action. 	<p>The BM will calculate and report the number of hours per day (e.g. 5) that the comfort readings were found outside the specified range as well as the particular timing of the low comfort condition (e.g. 10-12 am).</p>

Event	Trigger	Reaction	Validation
<p>'Low indoor air quality'</p>	<p>The event traces low air quality conditions. It does not seem necessary (but can add value) to trace presence as the event is equally interesting in non-presence conditions. The conditions considered are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CO₂ above a threshold - dust/ particles above a threshold <p>Not both options need to be simultaneously set and traced in the BM. Also, there is nothing restrictive in registering also other air quality parameters; yet these are the more common problems and they can be measured in a relatively cost- efficient way.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - via simple notification: The BM module issues a reminder and a recommendation to space users that have this type of notification ON; the notification can be received by all three standard channels; dashboard, e-mail, SMS. - via technology change: It does not appear possible to hardwire any predefined technology solution. If there are air quality issues one needs to understand their origin and then take action. <p>In some rare cases the CO₂ metering could be linked to the ventilation system; this however is a major overhaul and it is not suggested to be addressed directly by the BM itself.</p>	<p>The BM will calculate and report the number of hours per day (e.g. 5) that the quality readings were found outside the specified range as well as the particular timing of the low quality condition (e.g. 10-12 am).</p>

Table 8: HIT2GAP behaviour module specification

HIT2GAP behaviour module	
Purpose and rationale	<p>The behaviour module offers a number of services which are related to how users use:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the building spaces, • the building energy systems.
Users	<p>End users are the primary recipients of the BM services; it is their behaviour with regard to space use and energy systems that is primarily targeted.</p> <p>Obviously, facility and maintenance managers are also involved, although rather indirectly as potential supervisors of the module and the reaction it triggers as well as implementers of the technology interventions that may be decided.</p>
Conditions required for the implementation	<p>The BM has</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a number of event-driven functionalities; every event has its own requirements; • a mood identification functionality, whereby, via appropriate devices the mood of a number of users, bearing these devices, is registered and analysed. <p><u>Obligatory</u></p> <p>It is compulsory to set up the BM notification.</p> <p><u>Helpful but non obligatory</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commands to control the lighting via issuing an appropriate output signal (event 1). • Commands to controls the HVAC by changing the thermostat setting, in a two-step (MEDIUM/ LOW) manner; lowering it in winter and raising it in summer (event 2). <p>Space simulations would be required to translate the reduced heating/ cooling hours into energy savings (event 2).</p>
Data required	<p><u>Obligatory</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Readings for presence detector signal (event 1, 2, optionally 3 and 4). • Readings for ambient temperature, humidity, surface temperature, according to how this functionality will be used (event 3).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Readings for sensors for CO2 and/ or dust particles, according to how this functionality will be used (event 4). <p><u>Helpful but non obligatory</u></p> <p>Questionnaires to register the space users' definition of comfort would be a great added value when setting up the parameters in this event. It is well known that not all people consider comfort in the same way. Therefore setting the parameters of the event/ module by taking consideration of space users is a great added value.</p> <p>Unlike the comfort above, where users have their own perception of comfort, air quality figures are mostly unknown as concepts and/ or values; therefore it is unlikely that any background info via questionnaires makes any sense.</p>
<p>Output</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The dashboard registers and reports sensor data information in real time; it also reports events, when they occur. Events are also reported via sms / email notifications that can be set up via appropriate dashboard functionalities. <p>Questionnaire results can also be reported via the dashboard if the module manager considers this as necessary and helpful. System parameters must also be possible to report on the dashboard following the same approach as the questionnaire results.</p>
<p>User interface requirements</p>	<p>-</p>
<p>Other</p>	<p>About MOOD; Registering and reporting on user mood</p> <p>This is a non-event driven component; its purpose is to register and report on user mood, via a number of devices ported by the users. The "user mood" analysis will be based on a number of real time and contextual parameters being in our case</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Heart Rate; supplied by a health monitor Heart Rate Variability; extracted from the above real time parameter Contextual information such as <ul style="list-style-type: none"> user task user location user posture

4.4.5 Energy management

The Energy Management module (called hereafter 'the EM') has capability of supporting all aspects of the Energy Management System (EnMS) in a building or building stock, belonging to organizations of any type and size.

Even if the EnMS is realized by adopting automated and commercial cloud-based software (such as the Enerit software), the EM module within the HIT2GAP platform is designed to comply with the strategic perspective of displaying the main information to help the HIT2GAP user increase energy efficiency and reaching optimization.

The approach is modular and the module's reaction may include *notification to the users*, over data visualization. Notification is a key mechanism to comply with the ISO 50001 international standard, energy efficiency and process optimization.

The functionalities of the first version (EM version 1.0) to be implemented and demonstrated within the HIT2GAP project are:

- Data acquisition and remote monitoring received from external sources (Enerit software) on energy consumptions, device status, indoor comfort and alarm & faults to display the HIT2GAP information (visualized through integrated Sankey energy flow diagrams, tables and graphs (Figure 8), that allows the energy review process.
- Energy Management: The algorithm receives data from external sources (Enerit software) and reacts to display the HIT2GAP information that allows the identification of current energy sources, and baselines and Energy Performance Indicators (EnPIs).
- Action Management: The algorithm receives data from external sources (Enerit software) and reacts to display HIT2GAP information that allows the identification of the following ISO 50001 recommended items:
 - energy review process: evaluation of past and present energy use and consumption, information related to the creation of a Significant Energy Use (SEU)⁶,
 - capturing & prioritizing improvement opportunities for easy decision-making,
 - automated assignment of actions with target dates & reminders to energy team members,
 - management reports including energy and action status dashboard.
- Document Management: Management reports including both energy and action status

⁶ According to ISO 50001 "Significant Energy Usage" (SEU) captures information on the identified energy using processes and equipment in the organization or site. The information and the energy use are identified by an energy audit and are used to document the results of an energy audit. The objectives and targets for each energy user can be documented. Automated assignment of actions with target dates & reminders to energy team members has to be provided.

dashboard. Different document types can be created/stored in the cloud-based Software under the pillars of the ISO 50001 standard:

- Commitment, (e.g. Commitment Document, Energy Policy, Energy Manual, Roles and Responsibilities)
- Planning, (e.g. “legal and other requirements” documents).
- Implementation, (e.g. “operational control” documents).
- Checking (e.g. “evaluation of legal and other requirements” documents).

The integrated concept can be seen in Figure 8, gathering different views of the functionalities mentioned above.

Figure 8: The integrated concept of an overall solution for effective Energy Management

The EM module is for individual people who will benefit from new services or products and for groups that show interest in expanding their technical and managerial skills.

In general, target users are those organizations which:

- already adopt the ISO 50001, or want to certify to ISO 50001, or do not need certification but want to follow best practices,
- want to upgrade from home-built ISO information systems (e.g. spreadsheets and shared drives),
- want to go beyond simple energy monitoring to establish a systematic approach to energy management as a process.

The integration between the EM module in the HIT2GAP platform and the Enerit software can be seen in Figure 9.

Figure 9: The EM module through the integration between Enerit SW and the HIT2GAP system

Table 9: HIT2GAP Energy Management module specifications

HIT2GAP Energy Management module (EM)	
Purpose and rationale	<p>Energy Management Systems (<i>EnMS</i>) - and its related multi-years energy efficiency program are crucial for decision makers and stakeholders to remove barriers for energy efficiency while driving regeneration policies that stimulate for investments, especially in the current economic conditions.</p> <p>Within the HIT2GAP platform and the EM module - interfaced with the ISO 50001 EnMS - the process is identified and communicated to the users. Through the analysis of the energy data, deviations will be highlighted and decisions can be</p>

	<p>taken for corrective actions to be implemented in order to bring the EnMS under control and to guarantee a sustainable improvement (through training, updated communications etc.)</p>
<p>Users</p>	<p>The EM module will address the stakeholders that act to ensure the a more efficient energy management programme, namely:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public administrators and Policy makers, who overview cost savings, reward efforts to best energy classes, broadcast best energy management practices. These kinds of stakeholder also include the Smart City Community and promote solutions for achieving significant energy savings at district and city levels. - Operational, Energy, Facility, Environmental, Health, Safety & Quality Managers, who individually take decisions on how to manage the ongoing energy management process or to make the current operational scenario more effective. - Technicians, who have the day-by-day responsibility to maintain and operate the buildings. - ESCo and Financial Institutions, who could be interested in promoting concepts of green economy where energy savings pay for investments. - ICTs and Scientific Professionals, who develop and promote best practices and new technologies, while producing awareness on efficient scenarios and habits. <p>These type of users can be found either in industry (e.g. automotive, paper, healthcare, plastics, food & drink) as well as in the public/private sector buildings (such as airports, universities & schools, hospitals, banks, shopping centres, etc.), both managed as units (e.g. individual buildings or building stocks) or geographically scattered in a territory.</p>
<p>Conditions required for the implementation</p>	<p>The EM module offers the possibility to highlight gaps in the current energy management programme. The EM module is not a monitoring software. It relies on inputs from other sources, either manually input or through automated integration techniques.</p> <p>The EM module does not require any particular instrumentation. It puts together information coming from external ISO 50001 EnMS software packages to arrange and organize them in a way that suit with company needs to cover all phases of creating an energy action plan, implementation, customization, training, integration.</p> <p>The EM module v1.0 only needs Enerit SW interfaced with the HIT2GAP system. The overall integration concept is summarized as front/back-end integration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Link sub-meter data to <u>visualization module</u> for Energy Planning process. ○ Link alarm and warning data to <u>action management module</u> for systematic reporting, tracking and energy saving actions.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Links to other Energy Management software. - Links to other Management systems. - Single login to access both products.
Data required	<p>Data from the facility regarding energy consumptions, device status, indoor comfort and alarm & faults.</p> <p>Other data coming from Enerit software.</p>
Output	<p>The EM module issues to users that have configured into the HIT2GAP system a notification for any created action, and recommendation on how to implement and validate the implementation; following the whole life-cycle of the action: created, assigned to, on-going, for review, rejected, close. The user can receive the notification by all three standard channels: dashboard, e-mail, SMS.</p>
User interface requirements	-

4.4.6 Building performance simulation

The Building Performance Simulation (BPS) module comprises both models and simulation capabilities to the HIT2GAP platform. A model within the BPS module can be of comprehensive nature or may represent parts of the building or HVAC systems. A comprehensive building model can include building envelope, HVAC generation and distribution system, representation of the building users, weather variables, internal loads such as lighting and electricity. A model can also be developed to represent only certain parts or domains of a given building. In the latter case, parts which are not included in the model can be abstracted and constructed from input data files based on measurement data from the HIT2GAP database, data generated with other simulation tools, using surrogate models or a combination of them.

A given model within the BPS module should contain all necessary input files and required input data to run simulations, so it can run independently and does not exhibit dependencies on the HIT2GAP database to be used.

The model can be set up in any programming language or software package that is able to provide a HIT2GAP-compliant BPS module. The external representation of the BPS module and its interfacing methods within the HIT2GAP platform are decoupled from the source tool where the model was generated, so it does not depend on specific software tools.

The simulation models provided can generally be of diverse level of detail, ranging from detailed CFD-simulations to simplified resistance-capacity (RC) models.

Usage of the models in combination with other HIT2GAP modules needs provision of additional parameter settings to be stipulated beforehand. More precisely:

- For usage with the Uncertainty Analysis model, the **uncertain inputs** and their associated **uncertainty distributions** should be identified.
- For usage with the Calibration module, the **calibration parameters** should be identified.

Table 10: HIT2GAP Building Performance Assessment module specifications

HIT2GAP Building Performance Simulation	
Purpose and rationale	<p>The Building Performance Simulation (BPS) module provides the HIT2GAP platform with a model of a building and/or HVAC systems. Typically, the models provided are developed previously using any modelling tool or technique available.</p> <p>In general terms, the BPS module provides users with models that can be parameterized and simulated.</p> <p>The BPS module offers models and simulation functionalities that can be used alongside other HIT2GAP modules, such as the Uncertainty module or the Calibration module. Simulation results can be stored in the HIT2GAP databases. These results can be used in combination with other HIT2GAP data sets, especially those regarding actual data, in order to visualize data and produce comparisons between simulated and real measured variables.</p>
Users	<p>The BPS module can be used at different stages of the building lifecycle serving a variety of users. The main targeted user profiles are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design Engineers: the BPS module can be used for sizing systems and help decide between different design alternatives; • Commissioning Engineers: the BPS module can be used as a baseline to perform quality testing of the already built systems, and also to help setup an initial optimal control strategy using advanced methods; • Energy Managers: the BPS module can be used as a test bench for Energy Conservation Measures based on enhanced control and operation of HVAC systems, before they are implemented; • Facility Managers: the BPS can be used to perform continuous monitoring of building services to perform anomaly detection or routinely assess the correct state of systems and components.
Conditions required for the implementation	<p>Obligatory</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A common approach to interface different types of Building and/or HVAC simulation models, such as Energy+, ESP-r, Modelica, or others;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connection methods and rules to other modules of the HIT2GAP platform, with special attention to the Uncertainty Analysis (UA), calibration and visualization modules; • Connection method and rules to retrieve inputs from measurement data stored at the HIT2GAP database; • Available measurement data sets specific to any of the models provided. <p><u>Helpful but non obligatory</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A connection method to other type of simulation modules that are not necessary building and HVAC centred and may or may not exist in the HIT2GAP platform, such as Discrete Events, Markov Chain models, models providing stochastic weather forecasting and so forth; • A connection method to the User Behaviour module of the HIT2GAP platform.
<p>Data required</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building information. This can come from a diversity of data sources, for instance and non-exhaustively: typical default assumptions, as-built static data, BIM generated data, measurement campaigns, short term monitoring data, manufacturer data, or site-survey information. • Real measurement gathered data, of type, extent and quality which is dependent on the model developed.
<p>Output</p>	<p>Output results can vary according to the type of model developed, these results might be visualized using visualization modules of the HIT2GAP platform, saved to files, or stored and made available in the HIT2GAP database. Typical simulation outputs provided are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy consumption; • Energy demand, whereas thermal energy and/or electricity demand; • Zone temperatures; • Other physical parameters of interests.
<p>User interface requirements</p>	<p>The user interface of the BPS module should at least facilitate the following functionalities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A model presentation and content section where the user can identify model parameters, attributes and parameter properties. In this section the user is made aware of which model parameters can be changed in the existing model; • A simulation run configuration section where the user can setup simulation works with different purposes. This section may specify some parameters like simulation run period, simulation name and/or any other parameters which may be modified by the user.

4.4.7 Simulator-Calibration

The simulation software always includes an inherent simulation error. During the simulation process the technological object is replaced (simulated) sequentially by a theoretical model, a mathematical model, a numerical model and, finally, by an algorithmic model. The hypotheses and approximations taken following these different phases of transformations may generate some bias into the model. Other aspects that affect the accuracy of the simulation are:

- Poor representation of the innovative design features (such as radiant floors) and systems (underfloor-air, displacement ventilation, natural ventilation, heat exchange with neighbouring building etc.) in the simulation software.
- Lack of knowledge of real time usage of lighting and plug-loads. For instance, the significantly higher lighting and plug-loads reduce the heating loads and increase the cooling loads.
- Uncertainty in weather prediction. Weather plays a unique and significant role as it directly affects the thermal loads and thus energy performance of buildings.

As presented in the technical specification of the energy modelling approach in HIT2GAP in D1.5 [7], some authors say that a good model is accurate within 20% of the actual annual energy consumption, and a calibrated model is accurate within 5-10% of actual annual energy consumption. A calibrated model involves a process of using genuine as-built information, surveys and measured data to update the input parameters of the initial simulation model so that it closely represents the real operation of the building.

To alleviate the issue, HIT2GAP will include a simulator-calibration module with the capability to adjust the input parameters of a BPS model and reduce the gap between the prediction and the real measurements.

In brief, the procedure underlying the calibration module comprises the following steps:

- Obtain data defining building performance (DATA).
- Establish an as-built model (ABM).
- Simulate ABM.
- Report differences between ABM predictions and DATA in the form of a confidence interval ($\pm x C$, $\pm y \text{ kWh/m}^2$) for 90% of the time covered by DATA and assuming normally distributed errors.
- Divide DATA into a calibration (80%) and validation dataset (20%).
- Assign uncertainty to each model parameter using probability density distributions.
- Perform sensitivity analysis using the Morris method followed by the Sobol method.
- Identify influential inputs based on results of sensitivity analysis; retain model inputs explaining at least 70% of the model output variance.

- Perform Bayesian Calibration of the upgraded model for the most influential inputs, using Gaussian Process Regression and Markov Chain Monte Carlo methods to infer the best fit between input parameters and DATA.
- Create and report the calibrated model (CM) using best-fit input from the previous step.
- Perform analysis of the correlation between residuals and boundary conditions from DATA. Based on this analysis, identify and report possible additional improvements to CM using the Difference Analysis procedure.
- Report differences between DATA and CM.
- Deliver CM.

When necessary, the operations listed above can be carried out through calls to other modules to avoid redundancies within the HIT2GAP platform.

Table 11: HIT2GAP simulator-calibration module definition

HIT2GAP Simulator-Calibration module	
Purpose and rationale	This module provides the HIT2GAP platform with the capability to adjust the input parameters of a BPS model in order to improve the agreement between measured data and predictions.
Users	<p>The Calibration module can be used at any stage of the operational life of the building, as long as measured performance data are available. It can potentially be applied to any BPS tool and therefore a large number of user types may be supported such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Design Practitioners</u> – wishing to calibrate models prior to use to assess the performance of different design alternatives. • <u>Commissioning Engineers</u> – wishing to improve the definition of baseline performance or establish optimised set-point states for equipment control. • <u>Energy Managers</u> – wishing to evaluate energy efficiency options that might be cost-effectively deployed or to deploy a BPS tool in model predictive control mode. • <u>Facility Managers</u> – wishing to explore HVAC/building system alteration to respond to issues reported by occupants.
Conditions required for the implementation	<p>The requirements of the calibration module can be satisfied by means external to the HIT2GAP platform or through the HIT2GAP-enabled connection of the Uncertainty/Sensitivity and BPS Tool performance assessment modules.</p> <p><u>Obligatory</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capability of the BPS tool to run in script mode in order to generate the

	<p>multiple simulation results required as input to the calibration module.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The availability of measured data relating to weather boundary conditions. • The availability of measured data relating to the performance indicators that the BPS tool provides. <p><u>Helpful but non obligatory</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Further information on the operation of the building during the monitoring period.
<p>Data required</p>	<p>The data required can be obtained by means external to the HIT2GAP platform, or through HIT2GAP-enabled connectivity with the Uncertainty/Sensitivity and BPS Tool performance assessment modules.</p> <p><u>Obligatory</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A matrix (A) having as rows combination of the model parameters to calibrate randomly sampled according to certain design (Latin Hyper Cube Sampling design is advised). • A matrix (B) having as columns the boundary conditions to which the building was subject during the monitoring period. • A matrix (C) having as columns model simulations corresponding to the inputs in A and the boundary conditions in B. • A matrix (D) having as columns the measurements of the performance indicators that the model has to predict. <p><u>Helpful but not obligatory</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data on the operation of the building and eventual differences with the model.
<p>Output</p>	<p>The main outputs of the procedure are as follows.</p> <p><u>Sensitivity data necessary to assist calibration:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model parameter ranking. • Fixed parameters during the calibration and their values. • Model output variance attributable to the calibration parameters. • Model output variance attributable to the neglected (fixed) parameters. <p><u>Calibration:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Calibration parameters estimates and confidence intervals. • Goodness of fit of the model.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ranking of the boundary conditions depending on their correlation with the residuals.
User interface requirements	<p>The user interface of the calibration module should support:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> loading of the required data necessary to run the module; visualisation of results from the calibration process.

4.4.8 Uncertainty Analysis and Sensitivity Analysis

As introduced in previous sections, data coming from the field contains errors or is incomplete, either if it comes from sensors or from equipment or building specifications. The errors in the input data propagate through calculations leading to inaccuracy in the results. The uncertainty analysis investigates the uncertainty of variables that are used in decision-making problems in which observations and models represent the knowledge base. The uncertainty analysis module to be developed in HIT2GAP enables to run simulation models with a set of uncertain input parameters (e.g. building parameters, climate conditions, occupancy). The simulation results (e.g. energy consumption) are represented by probability distributions, according to the input probability distributions of the uncertain parameters. Making use of uncertainty analysis methods gives the user a more reliable simulation result, as input uncertainties are taken into account.

On the other side, the sensitivity analysis is the study of how the uncertainty in the output of a mathematical model or system (numerical or otherwise) can be apportioned to different sources of uncertainty in its inputs. Ideally, uncertainty and sensitivity analysis should be run in tandem that is why the module to be developed in HIT2GAP includes both analyses. The sensitivity method provided will allow for determining the impact of varying input parameters on the output variation. More precisely, it is estimated whether, for example, the room temperature set value or the g-value of the windows is more influential for the energy consumption of a given building.

The methodology can be divided into four steps:

- **Sampling:** Based on Sobol-Sequences a large number of samples is drawn from each input distribution.
- **Monte Carlo Simulation:** One simulation is run for each input combination. In order to speed up this process, several kernels can be used.
- **Uncertainty Analysis:** The results corresponding to all simulation runs are collected and visualized (or saved in a file) in terms of a probability distribution
- **Sensitivity Analysis:** Variance-based sensitivity indices are calculated for each input (and each output, if several are considered) and visualized (or saved in a file). Inputs with high sensitivity indices (close to one) correspond to highly influential inputs, whereas inputs with small sensitivity indices (close to zero) correspond to negligible inputs.

Table 12: HIT2GAP uncertainty and sensitivity analysis module specifications

HIT2GAP Uncertainty analysis module	
Purpose and rationale	<p>The uncertainty analysis module provides the possibility to run simulation models with a set of uncertain input parameters (e.g. building parameters, climate conditions, occupancy). The simulation results (e.g. energy consumption) are represented by probability distributions, according to the input probability distributions of the uncertain parameters.</p> <p>Making use of uncertainty analysis methods gives the user a more reliable simulation result, as input uncertainties are taken into account.</p> <p>Additionally, the module provides methods for sensitivity analysis, which allows for determining the impact of varying input parameters on the output variation. More precisely, it is estimated whether, for example, the room temperature set value or the g-value of the windows is more influential for the energy consumption of a given building.</p>
Users	<p>Energy managers. In principal, the module is also suited for usage in the planning phase by planning engineers which set up simulation models.</p>
Conditions required for the implementation	<p><u>Obligatory</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interaction between uncertainty analysis module and simulation module <p><u>Helpful but non obligatory</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passing of results to visualization module
Data required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A simulation model of the considered building (as executable or Functional Mockup Unit) or connection to simulation module via HIT2GAP. • Input files (e.g. user profiles, weather) to the simulation, if applicable. • Specification of uncertain input parameters with corresponding distributions: normal distribution with specified mean and standard deviation, uniform distribution with specified min and max values. • Specification of output(s) to be analysed (e.g. monthly energy consumption). • Number of kernels available for distribution of calculations. • Number of samples to be drawn from the input distributions.

	Obviously, the computational effort increases with increasing number of samples and decreasing number of available kernels.
Output	<p>For a given simulation model</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Output distribution(s) • Sensitivity indices for all inputs <p>Results might be visualized (passed to visualization module).</p>
User interface requirements	<i>to be developed</i>

4.4.9 Renewable Energy Simulator

In order to facilitate the integration of renewable sources in a facility, HIT2GAP will integrate a simulator module to support the user in the management of the energy coming from renewable sources and integrate it effectively in the installation. The module, named REnSIM, executes simulations using the following critical design parameters: historical meteorological data, building space availability data, energy use profiles and pricing data, specific RET (Renewable Energy Technology) configuration technical data and RET equipment installation data.

Within HIT2GAP, REnSIM will be upgraded into an advanced platform connected with BMS in order to use historical and real-time data from thermal and electrical energy producing and consuming devices to identify performance and detect faults in renewable systems. In addition, using actual historical and real-time user behavioural data, REnSIM will have the capability to identify any retrofits required.

The module has been developed further to operate with the HIT2GAP platform as a web based application and the computations are executed as individual web services that require specific input. The input is sent to the web services in JSON Format executed remotely and the results are delivered back to the module in the same format. The suggestion for the weather data retrieval from HIT2GAP Platform to REnSIM is by using Web Services.

REnSIM provides computations for three types of renewable systems:

1. Solar Thermal System: Hot Water,
2. Solar Thermal System: Space Heating System and
3. Solar Photovoltaic System.

The module requires data from the solar thermal system involving the specifications of the system, the location of the installation, the technical features of the building and the usage.

Some indicative screen shots to display outputs for the REnSIM can be seen in the following figures.

Figure 10: RenSIM Solar thermal output

Figure 11: RenSIM Solar space heating output

Figure 12: RenSIM PV output

Table 13: HIT2GAP Renewable Energy Simulator module specifications

HIT2GAP Renewable Energy Simulator (REnSIM) Module	
<p>Purpose and rationale</p>	<p>The Renewable Energy Simulator is a simulation environment which serves as a design aid or decision support tool for the design or retrofit of new or existing energy infrastructures in buildings through the estimation and prediction of energy production (both thermal and electrical). REnSIM provides computations for three types of renewable systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solar Thermal System: Hot Water • Solar Thermal System: Space Heating System • Solar Photovoltaic System

<p>Users</p>	<p>The REnSIM users are Building and Maintenance Managers, Energy Consultants, RET System Designers and manufacturers.</p>
<p>Conditions required for the implementation</p>	<p>The computations are dependent on the annual weather data for particular locations. Additionally, it is important to provide manufacturer's data that can be retrieved from the specification sheets and laboratory reports of the installed system. Users have to give approximations of their demands in water or room temperature per day in order to simulate the optimal energy consumption by each system.</p>
<p>Data required</p>	<p>Required Input Data for Simulation of Solar Thermal Systems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Renewable System data (Accredited Lab Report Data, EN 12975-2 / ISO 9806-1 and EN 12976-2): collector, hot water tank and system specifications • Location: city and country • External backup system COP (Coefficient of Performance) (Example: Gas boiler, oil boiler, heat pump) • Central heating designed temperatures (Temperature difference DT between inlet and outlet of the boiler) • Cylinder minimum temperature: Minimum temperature of the cylinder in order to avoid the starting of the back-up source. It is suggested to remain a fixed value not obvious for the user • Central heating operation months (on/off): Months of the year that the central heating is ON • Energy cost (kWh/Euro): Energy cost of the city – country (kWh/Euro) • Hourly average hot water demand (litres of hot water drawn off during an average day) • House heat losses (data for heated area and relevant u-values): wall m², roof m², floor m², windows m² and corresponding U-value [W/m²K] • Hourly desired room temperature of an average winter day <p>Required BMS Data for the performance calculation of Solar Thermal System Components (i.e collector, tank and system solar contribution)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solar Collector: The sensors needed for the measuring the collector performance are: temperature sensors at collector inlet and outlet and for measuring ambient temperature, SP Pyranometer for measuring the hemispherical solar irradiance G (Wxm⁻²), flow meter for measuring the flow between collector inlet and outlet • Solar Water Tank: The sensors needed for the measuring the tank heat losses are: immersed temperature sensor in 2/3 of storage tank and temperature sensor for ambient temperature, flow meter at tank outlet (hot water outlet) for verifying the zero drawn off • System Utilisation Factor % (Solar Contribution): The sensors needed

for measuring the system Utilisation Factor are the following:

- Tank: temperature sensors at hot water tank inlet and outlet, flow meter at at tank outlet, electricity meter
- Collector: temperature sensors at hot water tank inlet and outlet and ambient temperature, SP pyranometer for measuring the hemispherical solar irradiance G, flow meter for measuring the flow between collector inlet and outlet

Required Input Data for Simulation of Solar PV Systems

Y_{PV}	is the rated capacity of the PV array, meaning its power output under standard test conditions [kW]
f_{PV}	is the PV derating factor [%]
β	is the slope of the surface (0° horizontal, 90° vertical) [°]
γ	is the azimuth of the surface (South 0°, East -90°, West 90°, North 180°) [°]
λ	is the longitude [°]
ϕ	is the latitude [°]
ρ_g	is the ground reflectance, which is also called the albedo [%]
a_P	is the temperature coefficient of power [%/°C] *
A_{PV}	is the surface area of the PV module [m ²]
\overline{G}	is the global horizontal radiation on the earth's surface averaged over the time step [kW/m ²]
Z_c	is the time zone in hours east of GMT [hr]
T_a	is the ambient temperature [°C]
$T_{c,NOCT}$	is the nominal operating cell temperature [°C]**
LFT	is the PV lifetime [yrs]

Notes for PV System

* Regarding the a_P :

Usually should be provided by the constructor.

If not, then it should be calculated from the provided Power/temperature graph (slope).

Some product brochures do not specify the temperature coefficient of power, but do specify the temperature coefficient of the open-circuit voltage. In that case

$$a_P \approx \frac{\mu_{Voc}}{V_{mp}} \text{ where:}$$

	<p>μ_{Voc} is the temperature coefficient of the open-circuit voltage [V/°C]</p> <p>V_{mp} is the voltage at the maximum power point under standard test conditions [V]</p> <p>** Regarding the $T_{c,NOCT}$: Usually provided. Commonly 45°C to 48°C</p>
Output	<p>Solar thermal production</p> <p>Solar space heating</p> <p>PV production</p>
User interface requirements	<p>See figures above</p>

4.4.10 Multiple set-point control

The most affordable strategy (algorithms) for indoor thermal comfort (control) of individual building spaces (rooms or zones) is designed according to the room occupancy profiles and thresholds (set-point) for each physical variable (indoor temperature and humidity).

The main benefits of a control strategy that that takes into account occupancy are:

- Energy saving resulting from control actions that combine the real-time room/zone occupancy profile (occupant within the room) and the time extension of no occupancy, discriminating between short and long absence periods.
- Indoor thermal comfort: optimal when the occupant is in the room; stand-by (reduced) for short absence period of the occupant; economy (minimum) for long absence period of the occupant.
- A cost effective solution that integrates in a single input/output monitoring and control module the management capability of different physical devices working in the room, reducing at the same time the length of the wires.

Control algorithms are often characterized by the combination of several real-time *agents* such as *season*, *timetable*, *occupancy* and *set-point*.

- The *season agent* discriminates about heating or cooling requirements.
- The *timetable agent* establishes scheduled time intervals to switch on/off the heating/cooling system.
- The *occupancy agent* detects the user's presence in the controlled space, based on the information provided from any presence sensor installed within the room.

- The *set-points agent* checks the measured temperature value versus the set-point (a \pm swing around the set-point value is established to reward the user's preferences without disregarding the rules imposed by the energy manager).

The module to be developed in HIT2GAP introduces innovation and progress beyond the commercial state of the art of existing Building Management Systems (BMS) by considering a closed loop control strategy for heating/cooling designed on three set-points levels: *comfort*, *stand-by* and *economy* for combining energy saving and thermal indoor comfort, mostly in building spaces where the occupancy profile is variable over time. The control algorithm will add a new agent *delay* to define other thresholds (set-points) that account for the short and long period (time delay) of no user presence in the room. The short and long time delays are to be set in each room according to the user's activity and behaviour.

The combination of *season*, *timetable*, *occupancy*, *delay*, and *set-point agents* allows to design the closed loop control strategy by regulating the indoor temperature (*thermal agent*) as follows:

- The thermal agent switches OFF the system or the local sub-system when,
 - according to the *timetable agent* it should be OFF, or
 - the *set-points agent* detects, through the measured temperature, that there is no need to maintain the *comfort* set-point any longer, in accordance with the information detected by the *occupancy agent*.
- The thermal agent switches ON the system or the local sub-system
 - a. to maintain the indoor temperature around the *comfort* set-point [value + swing] when,
 - the *occupancy agent* detects presence inside the room, and
 - the *set-points agent* detects, through the measured temperature, that there is a need to scale up towards that level (from the *economy* or *stand-by* levels);
 - b. to reduce the indoor temperature around the *stand-by* set-point when,
 - the *occupancy agent*, in combination with the *delay agent*, detects short time absence inside the room, and the *set-points agent* detects, through the measured temperature, that there is a need to scale down towards that level (from the *comfort* level);
 - c. to reduce the indoor temperature around the *economy* set-point when,
 - the *occupancy agent*, in combination with the *delay agent*, detects long time absence inside the room, and the *set-points agent* detects, through the measured temperature, that there is a need to scale down towards that level.
- The thermal agent leaves the system or the local sub-system UNCHANGED (whatever is the output of the timetable agent),

- the set-points agent detects, through the measured temperature, that there is no need to scale up or down the current set-point, in accordance with the information detected by the occupancy agent.

The operation of such a strategy is depicted in Figure 13

Figure 13: Closed loop control strategy with comfort, stand-by and economy set-points for multi-setpoint module

Additionally, other conditions represented by corresponding agents can be taken into account, to enhance the control strategy such as:

- **Condensation:** a humidity sensor can be placed in the proximity of the cold air inlet vents to detect any condensation (too much moist air) effect and determine the conditions for a possible suspension of control actions.
- **Windows:** all these control strategies can be integrated with a new agent called windows. The windows agent controls the status (open/closed) of the windows, if magnetic contacts are installed on their frames, and provides further inputs to the thermal agent to determine the cases of switching off or regulate at minimum level the air conditioning system (heating or cooling) while windows are left opened.
- **Shading device:** in the context of energy efficiency and indoor comfort in building spaces, the solar control by means of shading devices (fixed, mobile, internal or external) is an efficient technique that allows benefits from the solar effects. The control of the solar gain through the windows (shading device) has an impact on the environmental conditions, to

improve both the thermal and visual indoor comfort, and the energy saving, through the reduction of heating, cooling and electrical loads. Thus, the primary objectives of an optimal shading device agent (controller) for thermal comfort may:

- allow the maximum exploitation of solar gains through windows in winter, or preventing overheating in summer, when the user is not present;
- act to move the blind if there is a significant difference between the temperature set-point and the actual position, so to keep the shading device movements at minimum.

Thermal rule-based concepts of the *shading device agent*, when the user is not present, assist the *thermal agent* (heating/cooling control) in choosing the best possible blind position to exploit solar gains in winter (up to the maximum aperture) and to avoid overheating in summer (up to the maximum closure).

Table 14: HIT2GAP multi-setpoint control module specifications

HIT2GAP Multi-setpoint control	
Purpose and rationale	<p>In order to enhance energy efficiency and indoor thermal comfort and provide a cost-effective solution in the control of heating and cooling, there is a need to implement a more advanced control strategy that takes into account several parameters to reduce energy consumption without compromising thermal comfort.</p> <p>The multi-setpoint control module aims at maintaining different indoor comfort profiles as a function of the occupancy profiles (user presence/absence of personnel) within the reference space through the adjustment of a 3-way valve or a by-pass damper (thermostatic valve).</p> <p>The control strategy considers season (cooling/heating), timetable, occupancy, indoor temperature, and indoor humidity to set a three-level set-point (optimal/stand-by/economy) according to short or long term unoccupancies.</p> <p>Eventually the thermal control strategy can be combined with a shading strategy to optimise the shades position for thermal gain.</p>
Users	All the stakeholders involved in the Building Management System (BMS), e.g. Software Designers, System Integrators, Energy Managers, Facility Managers.
Conditions required for the implementation	<p>The module applies to both existing and new BMS installations. In the former case, the firmware within the control module has to be updated; in the latter case the module becomes a requirement for purchasing in the market the BMS.</p> <p>The control algorithm can manage both thermostatic valves (ON/OFF control) and</p>

	<p>3-way valves.⁷</p> <p>The control algorithm can manage both devices with two pipes (discriminating heating from cooling) and devices with four pipes (contemporary heating and cooling).</p> <p>Presence sensors, ambient temperature thermostat, with temperature sensor and touches to select the temperature set-points, control valves for the cooling system (3-way valve, thermostatic valve, by-pass damper), control valves for the heating system (3-way valve, thermostatic valve, by-pass damper) are required. Optionally, sensor contact, motors to drive the vertical position of the blinds and the slats orientation can be considered.</p>
Data required	<p>Obligatory</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> indoor ambient data (temperature/ humidity) Set-points <p><u>Helpful but non obligatory</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Windows contact Venetian position and slats orientation
Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A Digital signal (ON/OFF) or analogue signal (in the range of 4-20 mA or 0-10V)
User interface requirements	-

4.5 The Visualization Interface

Recent studies in the field of energy efficient buildings have shown that the user behaviour in commercial buildings can have a significant impact on building energy use, and as a result, significant energy saving opportunities could be reached by influencing the building users to adopt energy conservation practices. There is therefore a high interest in understanding thoroughly what kind of users are present in buildings, what their needs in terms of tasks and thermal comfort are, how they typically behave with respect to energy related questions and what methods and technologies are available to better capture and influence their behaviour in a sustainable way while preserving their privacy.

⁷ In the scope of HIT2GAP it is not envisioned to automatically apply control commands; instead notifications can be sent and let the operators to apply them at their convenience.

A way to influence positively the user behaviour in regard to energy issues is providing them an easy and intuitive access to real-time and historical energy consumption data through visualization techniques. The access to these data can allow technical users like facility or energy managers to better conduct their tasks by identifying easily flaws and weaknesses of the building services but also help e.g. normal office workers to control and manage their individual consumption patterns.

Visualization modules play a crucial role as they deliver the final information to users, after the data coming from different analytic modules have been processed and prepared. This information shall be represented in different formats according to the data form and content and to the user's role and tasks in the building.

The display modules integrated in HIT2GAP will deliver an advanced visualization of energy- and comfort-related data for technical users and non-expert users. They will display customized performance indicators to support technical tasks and to improve the user's awareness related to the impact of their behaviour on the energy operation of buildings.

The display modules need to access a database/other modules where all energy and building services data are stored and pre-processed (e.g. aggregated energy data, calculated Energy Performance Indicators (EnPis), simulation results, FDD outputs, forecast data (e.g. weather, energy...)). Some notifications can also be included in the interface in order to support the end-users in taking the best decision in terms of energy management.

The initial definition of the technical specifications of the display modules that will be developed and integrated in the HIT2GAP solution is described in the deliverable D1.7 where the technical specification of display modules is described [3]. State-of-the-art and advanced visualization techniques for energy-related data have been selected and their features, fields of applications, advantages and disadvantages as well as typical end-users have been described. Additionally, a review and an analysis of bad and good practices in available visualization tools have been carried out with the objective to identify efficient techniques and common pitfalls at an early stage of the project.

It is planned to develop and integrate four visualization modules for the following applications in HIT2GAP:

- Energy Management
- Facility Management
- Building Occupants information
- 3D-Visualization

The development of the different modules will be based on a user-centric development approach whose methods and phases are described in D1.7 [3]. This approach has been initially conducted to identify user requirements and interests from different building stakeholders in the four HIT2GAP demonstration sites. Generic use-cases have been derived from this first analysis.

The next steps of the user-centric development approach will be applied during the module development and demonstration phases. In parallel, a validation methodology will be defined based

on the initial usability techniques presented along the above mentioned deliverable. This validation should quantify as much as possible the measurement of usability metrics and deliver an assessment of the capabilities of each visualization environment. The validation will be carried out by considering the above mentioned use-cases.

The next development steps for the visualization modules are:

- **The creation of initial mock-ups:** the mock-ups will be elaborated on the basis of the identified user requirements (energy managers, facility managers, building occupants, etc.). They will be enhanced by means of iterations with the end users.
- **Development of initial prototypes.** Once the mock-ups have been validated and refined by considering the users feedback from the demonstration sites, initial prototypes will be created and demonstrated.
- **Development, demonstration and validation of the final prototypes:** The prototypes will be further developed on the basis of the feedback from the use of the initial prototypes. They will be implemented in the demonstration sites and validated according to the validation methodology.

5 HIT2GAP methodology applied to pilot sites

As mentioned previously, it is not possible to develop a unique BMS that can cover the needs of all buildings because the features of the buildings, by type, location and construction characteristics are diverse. The approach taken in HIT2GAP to overcome this issue is to develop an open platform that can be customized by selecting the application modules needed, or extended with new third party modules that cover new functionalities and allow integration with legacy systems in place.

To demonstrate the flexibility offered by HIT2GAP the pilot sites chosen are located in different countries with different climates and construction years. The managers of the demo sites themselves have also different expectations on how HIT2GAP could help to enhance energy efficiency in their buildings.

The next sub-sections present the main features of the pilot sites and the use-case to be demonstrated according to pilot site manager's interests.

5.1 Challenger Campus pilot site

The location

The Challenger Campus demonstration building is located in Saint-Quentin-en-Yvelines, in France. Saint-Quentin-en-Yvelines is a new town in the French *département* of Yvelines. It is one of the original five *villes nouvelles* (new towns) of Paris and was named after the Saint Quentin Pond, which was chosen to become the town's centre. The town was built from a greenfield site starting in the 1960s. In 2007, Saint-Quentin-en-Yvelines had a population of 146,598. It is part of the much larger Paris metropolitan area, and is about 25 km west of the centre of Paris.

Figure 14: Challenger campus pilot site location

The climate in Saint-Quentin-en-Yvelines is moderate and influenced by the sea. It is a typical Western European oceanic climate, mild and wet.

The building

The Challenger is the headquarters of Bouygues construction. It was built in 1988 and renovated in 2014. It is certified with HQE®, LEED® Platinum, and BREEAM® Outstanding.

The insulation of the buildings is upgraded: 88% of the cladding glass (24,000m²) was replaced by a double-skin façade.

The heating and air conditioning of the buildings use as their primary energy sources the energies naturally present in the ground (ground-source) and air (air-source). Part of the electricity necessary for the operation of the site is produced locally by installing 25,000 m² of photovoltaic panels (dual PV-T solar panels on roofs).

Figure 15: Challenger Campus view

Wastewater and rainwater are treated by filtering gardens, artificial wetlands which purify water naturally for re-use on site.

The site is composed by 3 main buildings (3 floors and 2 basements), covering an area of 65,000 m², used as offices by 3,200 people.

Regarding the organization of the space, there are small rooms, open space offices and meeting rooms.

The energy sources used by the building are ground-source, photovoltaic, thermal solar, electricity and a thermal generator (security).

All buildings and the area are managed by the Hypervision BMS which supervises air conditioning, lighting, ventilation, heating ventilation, sanitary water, hot sanitary water, and technical alarms (Freon gases and water leakage, technical defect...).

The use case

The facility management team needs a system able to analyse the collected data over a reference period, to accurately forecast the building energy consumption and to be able to signal a malfunction before it becomes obvious. Such a tool will also enable a dynamic modification of the BMS set-up, in order to closely adapt it to all the operation condition changes: E.g., turn on or off the air-conditioning depending of the forecasted outside temperature in the coming hours. The existing algorithms like multiple linear regressions have proven to be insufficient: tests done by BES and research in scientific publications show significant deficiencies, but solutions like hybrid models between data mining approaches and thermal structural modelling should be able to solve these issues. During HIT2GAP, BES plans enhance Hypervision® through the integration of fault detection and diagnosis, building performance simulation, occupant behaviour, forecasting and the improvement of visualization tools. Data collected with Hypervision® will be used to evaluate and tune the various algorithms.

5.2 NanoGUNE pilot site

The location

The NanoGUNE demonstration building is located in Donostia-San Sebastián (Basque: Donostia, Spanish: San Sebastian). It is the capital city of the province of Gipuzkoa, in the Basque Country, Spain. Its population is 186,000 and the population of its metropolitan area is 436,000.

The city is in the North of Spain, on the southern coast of the Bay of Biscay. San Sebastián's picturesque coastline makes it a popular beach resort. Adding to the seaside environment, it benefits from hilly surroundings easily available.

Figure 16: NanoGUNE pilot site location

The city sits at the mouth of the River Urumea. Donostia has been built to a large extent over wetlands of the river during the last couple of centuries, with the city's downtown and the areas of Amara Berri and Riberas de Loiola lying on such terrain and the former bed of the river diverted to its current canalized course (first half of the 20th century).

Donostia-San Sebastián presents a mesothermal climate, moderate in terms of temperatures, and rainy. It is called humid temperate climate without dry season, or Atlantic climate.

The building

NanoGUNE is a nanoscience cooperative research centre where scientists, students, facility managers, and external companies work. A unique infrastructure of 7,000 m² is set up to host a cleanroom of nearly 300 m², 15 ultra-sensitive laboratories with state-of-the-art equipment and offices. The building was built in 2008. It is composed of a tower with 5 floors that contains offices

and another building with 2 floors containing offices, laboratories and a clean room. Currently about 170 people from more than 20 different countries are working in the NanoGUNE building.

Figure 17: NanoGUNE view

Regarding the space distribution, there are offices with open spaces and small rooms.

The energy sources used by the building are natural gas and electricity, and a small solar panel system is installed for domestic hot water.

For heating production there are two gas boilers VISSMAN Vitoplex 300 of 460 kW and for cooling production there is one Air/Water Daikin ALS F XE 327 XN chiller of 1.235 kW with heat recovery.

The building has different types of lamps of several types and power. The whole lighting installation is controlled by a KNX system, centralized where it is possible to see the use of each luminaire and act on them. In the bathrooms and in the hallway between the tower and the principal building there are presence sensors. On the stairs there are presence sensors combined with photocells to optimize the use of lighting in this area.

The ventilation is made by air conditioner for offices, laboratories. For ultra clean rooms, there are extractors for process hoods.

The sanitary hot water is produced by a heat exchanger of 27 kW and an inertial tank of 1.000 l and by solar panels.

The access of rooms is by electronic key, there are 2 lifts.

The HVAC, lighting system and access control are monitored. There is a BMS on site, but currently it is in process of being updated.

The use case

Since the installation of commissioning of the building a high consumption of gas and electricity has been observed. Currently, there is no adequate measurement and control system that allows for

identifying the cause of such consumption. Thanks to the solutions proposed by HIT2GAP, it is expected to detect and reduce the cause of this overconsumption. Some of the measures that are envisioned to adopt in order to reduce gas and electricity consumption are:

- Limit the thermostat set-point via the BMS. Currently all thermostats are controlled by users.
- Change the location of thermostats and/or increase temperature sensors to have a more representative value of indoor temperature in rooms that are very big.
- Use blinds in the windows to increase thermal comfort.
- Target user behaviour change to avoid the entrance door left open (installation of sensors can be helpful).
- Monitor the pumping consumption in order to know energy savings with a retrofit analyser module.
- Shift from having 4 different SCADA in different devices, (HVAC, lighting, access control and building alarms) to a multivariable statistical monitoring module.
- Monitor efficiently building occupancy and use it to implement energy efficient measurements such as controlling HVAC according to occupancy.

5.3 City Hall Wilanów pilot site

The location

The demonstration building is located in Warsaw, Poland. Warsaw is the capital and largest city of Poland. It lies on the Vistula River in east-central Poland, roughly 260 kilometres from the Baltic Sea and 300 kilometres from the Carpathian Mountains. Its population is estimated at 1.740 million residents within a greater metropolitan area of 2.666 million residents, which makes Warsaw the 9th most-populous capital city in the European Union. The city limits cover 516.9 km².

Figure 18: City Hall Wilanów pilot site location

Warsaw's climate is humid continental with cold, snowy, cloudy winters and warm, sunny, stormy summers, bordering on an oceanic climate.

The building

The building was built in 2014. It is composed by a ground floor, 3 floors, and an underground garage. It is used as offices by on average 137 people (permanent and non-permanent occupants). Regarding space organization there are small rooms, conference rooms, and a reception area.

Figure 19: City Hall Wilanów view

The energy sources on site are district heating and electricity. The heating is powered by district heating while the cooling is electrical, with 4 chillers. Sanitary hot water is supplied by the hot water district network.

The lighting system is controlled by a DALI system in the offices and it is manual in the rest of the building.

There is a BMS (UNIART) in place that controls air conditioning, lighting, ventilation, and temperature.

The use case

Wilanów Town Hall needs to know the exact amount of water, heat and electricity used and forecasted for the next months. This functionality will help to sign more beneficial contracts with suppliers. The bills may be lower thanks to adjusting HVAC to outdoor conditions, indoor temperature and number of people occupying the rooms/offices or particular zones. That is why there is a need to measure these parameters and give feedback to the facility management to allow them to set optimal temperatures or turn off air condition in areas empty for a long time. The system should inform about potential saving resulting from changing HVAC settings on a display. Information about current energy use and how far the building is from optimal performance should be displayed as well. The City of Warsaw proposed to install display panels in particular offices to give feedback directly to the end users to inform that e.g. changing HVAC setting may give better comfort, savings and will have a positive influence on health. Other sets of displays should be installed in corridors to show general information about current or daily average energy use in the whole building. The HIT2GAP tools should help to change users' habits and extend awareness that the energy conservation decreases CO₂ emissions, reduces the use of fossil fuels and gives tangible benefits. Data from a few years should be stored to compare energy use (taking outside temperature into account). It will help to indicate the areas which consume too much energy and point out where insulation has deteriorated. This functionality may be especially useful in the conference room.

Moreover, the HIT2GAP solution should integrate all existing meters and give possibility to add new ones.

5.4 NUIG pilot site

The location

The premises of the National University of Ireland to be piloted in HIT2GAP are located in Galway. Galway is a growth centre city in the West of Ireland in the province of Connacht. Galway lies on the River Corrib between Lough Corrib and Galway Bay and is surrounded by County Galway. It is the fourth most populous urban area in the Republic of Ireland and the sixth most populous city in the island of Ireland.

According to the 2016 Irish Census, Galway city has a population of 79,504; however, the rural county agglomeration is far bigger at 179,048.

Figure 20: NUIG pilot site location

Galway has a year-round mild, moist, temperate and changeable climate, due to the prevailing winds of the North Atlantic Current. It has a Maritime Temperate climate.

The building

The building chosen for demonstration purposes is the New Engineering building of the National University of Ireland, which was officially opened in 2011. It is a teaching and research facility with offices, classrooms and labs. The building has 4 floors and regarding space arrangement, it has 400

classrooms, including 3 large tiered and 25 breakout zones for group learning. It is used by 1,100 students and 110 staff members.

Figure 21: NUIG New Engineering Building view

The energy sources on site are electricity, natural gas, biomass, district heating and solar.

Lighting is controlled automatically according to ambient luminance and occupancy and schedules.

The ventilation is done through natural stack ventilation and climate wall with top-vented stack control and solar control via blinds.

Currently there is a BMS in place (Cylon Controls) which controls HVAC, natural ventilation and lighting. The BMS has 2086 sensors logging.

The use case

From a building energy manager's perspective, it is necessary to gauge a building's performance over time relative to an expected performance. It is the aim of the pilot site to integrate the Fault Detection and Diagnosis, Forecasting, and Building Simulation modules with Aspect Energy⁸ product developed by Cylon. Simulated and forecasted usage for a meter will be available via the Building Simulation module and Forecasting module web services respectively as target data in Aspect Energy. The development of targets feature will evaluate the HIT2GAP data relative to the actual data; this will allow visualization of reports to show actual usage vs. target and overspend evaluation. The targets will be used to demonstrate the suitability of the computed targets (simulation, or forecast) for selected meters.

⁸ Aspect Energy is a SaaS product which will be developed as part of the HIT2GAP engagement. It will analyse energy data captured from the NUIG pilot site, and provide some supervision capability for the target site remotely. This system, and its peripherals, will integrate with the HIT2GAP platform.

6 Conclusions

The present document presents the synthesis of HIT2GAP methodology derived from the work conducted within WP1 in terms of requirements definition, framework and methodology to perform energy savings based on the extraction of information from data gathered in buildings.

As presented, in order to improve the energy performance of a building and reduce the gap between expected and measured energy consumption, a new approach for building management systems is required, avoiding the traditional closed proprietary systems of most current BMS manufacturers. Following the approach of smartphones operating systems (Android and iOS), HIT2GAP proposes a solution composed of a core platform that enables seamless connectivity between the field level and the management level and a set of application modules that can be extended by any third party. The collection of application modules to be developed and tested in the first version of HIT2GAP has been selected according to user requirements and existing solutions from Consortium partners enabling the integration of state-of-the-art technologies and the extraction of knowledge from data that can be used by buildings users to optimize the building energy performance.

In order to adapt to the specific features of the buildings, the solution must be configurable and should provide the tools to interconnect with existing systems and indicators to support the decision making process.

Once the foundations of HIT2GAP solutions have been set, the next steps that will be carried out by the Consortium are the development of the platform core, of the different application modules, and the integration of all the components before the demonstration and validation in the four pilot sites.

7 References

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8 Glossary and acronyms

ABM	As-Built Model
AC	Alternate Current
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AOC	Abnormal Operating Conditions
API	Application Programming Interface
BEMS	Building Energy Management System
BES	Bouygues Energies & Services
BIM	Building Information Modeling
BM	Behaviour Module
BMS	Building Management System
BPS	Building Performance Simulation
CC	Correlation Coefficient
CM	Calibrated Model
COP	Coefficient of Performance
CSV	Comma Separated Variable
CYL	Cylon Controls
DB	Data Base
DMKD	Data Mining Techniques for Knowledge Discovery
DOA	Document of Action
ECM	Energy Conservation Measure
EM	Energy Management
EnMS	Energy Management System
EnPI	Energy Performance Indicator
EPC	Energy Performance Contracting
EPG	Energy Performance Gap
ESCo	Energy Service Company
FDD	Fault Detection & Diagnosis
FM	Facility Manager
FMI	Functional Mock-up Interface
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
HVAC	Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning

ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes
IPMVP	International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol
IoT	Internet of Things
MAPE	Mean Absolute Percentage Error
MEP	Mechanical Electrical Plumbing
MLP	Multilayer Perceptron
MLR	Multiple Linear Regression
MM	Maintenance Manager
M&V	Measurement and Verification
NOC	Normal Operation Conditions
NUIG	National University of Ireland in Galway
PC	Personal Computer
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
PV-T	Photovoltaic and Thermal
REnSIM	Renewable Energy Simulator
RET	Renewable Energy Technology
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SMS	Short Message Service
SVR	Support Vector Machine
XML	Extensible Markup Language

9 Appendices

9.1 Appendix 1: Questionnaire submitted to the different stakeholders in order to collect end users' requirements

QUESTIONNAIRE

The main purpose of HIT2GAP is to elaborate and develop new methods and tools for the better assessment of energy use within a building or a block of buildings in order to **minimize the gap between the theoretical and measured building performance**. In its essence, HIT2GAP aims at an open approach for **a new generation of BMS and data treatment solutions** with plug and play analytics tools and modular services using a win-win strategy (between service providers, BMS manufacturers and cutting-edge SMEs). In other words, SMEs can develop and integrate tools, algorithms or services within a holistic open framework while the HIT2GAP platform integrates the modules to provide a new generation of BMS. Further, elements of HIT2GAP, such as extended building simulation, can support the design phase to diminish the gap between the expected and the real performances.

The following questions have the objective to identify the needs and challenges faced by the relevant user types and the useful features that would facilitate their activities.

TYOLOGY OF USER

Please select what profession/function best describes you:

Facility Manager		Energy Service Company (ESCO)	
Energy Manager		Building Management System (BMS) provider	
Maintenance Manager		Technology or service providers	
Architect		Building Owner	
Mechanical, electrical, and plumbing services (MEP) Engineer		Building Tenant/Worker/Visitor	
Commissioning Engineer			

QUESTIONS

1. What are the main challenges of your job from a functional/technical point of view as regards to energy management?

2. Which functional/technical needs do you have in order to simplify and facilitate your job as regards to energy management?

- Predict the energy consumption needs
- Conduct dynamic modification of the BMS settings in order to adapt it to changes
- Have the supporting information to define concrete measures to reduce energy consumptions
- Improve the BMS capabilities with data processing/treatment functionalities
- Carry out an agile collection of data, through the use of alternative sensors and meters (i.e. smart phones, mobile phones, laptops, etc.)
- Analyse the current energy consumptions in comparison to a given period or reference building
- Optimize the demand/supply match with respect to the local RES supply
- Need to detect in advance the slow decrease in energy performance

- Need to detect malfunctions and anomalies in building operation
- Optimize the maintenance interventions by suggesting need for intervention
- Raise awareness among building occupants
- Consider building occupants' feedbacks with respect to the energy and comfort management
- Have the supporting data to assess the soundness of occupants' complaints
- Follow up and master the energy consumptions within an Energy Performance Contract
- Develop an energy management process (ISO 50001)
- OTHER (please specify)

3. Which features would you like to be implemented in a Building Management System with post processing functionalities to meet your needs?

- Energy Use Prediction supported by weather forecasts with data treatment analysis
- Integration with calibrated Building Energy Simulation
- Energy data collector and pre-processing (e.g., normalisation, codification)
- Energy data disaggregation
- Interoperability with alternative sensors and meters (i.e. smart phones, mobile phones, laptops, etc.)
- Integration with BIM database to store and visualise relevant information
- Building equipment control optimisation
- Fault detection and diagnosis to support in the identification of improvable settings
- Determine user comfort (ASHRAE 55 - EN 15251) to assess conditions and soundness of complaints
- Understand occupant's behaviour supported by distributed occupancy meters
- Management of Energy Performance Contract (e.g., via IPMVP)
- Integration with ISO 50001 management platform or green certification schemes (e.g, LEED, BREEAM)

OTHER (please specify)

4. What are your expectations of a post processing platform Building Management System with post processing functionalities?

5. What are the current practices related to the energy management of the buildings that you manage or in which you are involved?

9.2 Appendix 2: Main results and figures derived from the collected answers to the questionnaire

QUESTION 2:

Figure 22: Results for users' need to predict consumption

Figure 23: Results for users' need to have supporting information to reduce energy consumption

Figure 24: Results for users' need for agile data collections

Figure 25: Results for users' need to compare energy consumption between periods

Figure 26: Results for users' need to detect changes in energy performance

Figure 27: Results for users' need to detect anomalies and malfunctions

Figure 28: Results for users' need to consider occupants' feedback

Figure 29: Results for users' need to assess occupants' complaints

Figure 30: Results for users' need to follow up an EPC

Figure 31: Results for users' need to develop an energy management process

QUESTION 3

Figure 32: Results for users' need to integrate with calibrated Building Energy Simulation

Figure 33: Results for users' need for energy data collection and pre-processing

Figure 34: Results for users' need for energy data disaggregation

Figure 35: Results for users' need for interoperability with alternative sensors

Figure 36: Results for users' need to integrate with BIM

Figure 37: Results for users' need to optimise building equipment control

Figure 38: Results for users' need for fault detection and diagnosis support

Figure 39: Results for users' need to determine user comfort

Figure 40: Results for users' need to understand occupant's behaviour

Figure 41: Results for users' need to integrate with ISO 50001 or green certification schemes